

POI Descriptions for Leisure Walking Using Images and Contextual Embedding

by

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Abstract

Leisure walking is an important outdoor activity that benefits psychological, cognitive, and physical well-being, while also serving as a geographical phenomenon that connects people with spatial environments and places. In this context, walkers' experiences are shaped by Points of Interest (POIs) along the route, and walkers often seek information about POIs along a route before their journey. However, descriptive information about POIs is often missing or insufficient, particularly for lesser-known POIs. This limits the walkers' ability to plan and engage with their routes. It is therefore desirable to support automated generation of rich POI descriptions.

Existing approaches to POI description generation have received little attention to the leisure walking context and have not incorporated visual modalities in their solutions. Incorporating the leisure walking context into the generation process enables descriptions that better reflect walkers' interests and experiences, while the integration of images contributes to capturing the visual appearance of POIs more effectively. This research aims to develop a multimodal framework that integrates user interests, POI imagery, and spatial context to automatically generate POI descriptions tailored to the perspectives of individuals engaged in leisure walks.

By leveraging data from the WalkingMaps platform¹, we build a transformer-based encoder-decoder model that extends existing multimodal generation frameworks by integrating Vision Transformer encoding for POI images and contextual signals representing walkers' perspectives extracted from narrative descriptions. This architecture enables generating descriptions that capture the physical features of POIs, the atmosphere of their surroundings, and the interests of walkers.

This work contributes to advancing AI-generated POI descriptions that support leisure walkers in route planning and provide richer human-computer interaction with digital walking guides.

¹<https://walkingmaps.com.au/>

Declaration of Authorship

I, Thi Minh Hoai Bui, declare that this thesis titled, ‘POI Descriptions for Leisure Walking Using Images and Contextual Embedding’ and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

- This thesis does not incorporate without acknowledgment any material previously submitted for a degree or diploma in any university; and that to the best of my knowledge and belief it does not contain any material previously published or written by another person where due reference is not made in the text
- Where necessary I have received clearance for this research from the University’s Ethics Committee and have submitted all required data to the School
- The thesis is **25,809** words in length (excluding text in images, table, bibliographies and appendices)

Signed: THI MINH HOAI BUI

Date: 30/10/2025

Preface

Part of the research presented in this thesis has been submitted in abstract form to the special issue of the journal *Spatial Cognition and Computation (SCC)*. The abstract was submitted in September 2025, and the full manuscript is currently under development. The forthcoming article will further elaborate on some of the ideas and findings discussed in this thesis, particularly in the context of multimodal POI description generation and the influence of geo-context representations.

All other content in this thesis is original and was completed solely by the author. No editorial assistance was received in the preparation of this thesis. This research did not receive any external funding or financial support.

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Abbreviations

AI	A rtificial I ntelligence
API	A pplication P rogramming I nterface
BERT	B idirectional E ncoder R epresentations from T ransformers
BLEU	B ilingual E valuation U nderstudy
CACNN	C ontext- A ware C onvolutional N eural N etwork
CIDEr	C onsensus-based I mage D escription E valuation
CNN	C onvolutional N eural N etwork
COCO	C ommon O bjects in C ontext
CRNN	C onvolutional R ecurrent N eural N etwork
DB	D ifferentiable B inarization
DEN-RAD	D ensity-Aware R adius
FIX-RAD	F ixed R adius
GCN	G raph C onvolutional N etwork
GSGM	G uide- S elect G enerative M odel
GPT-2	G enerative P re-trained T ransformer 2
LLM	L arge L anguage M odel
LBF	L inear B imodal F usion
M3PA	M ultimodal P OI S emantic A nnotation
MMDG	M ulti- M odal D escription G enerator
MRR	M ean R eciprocal R ank
NLG	N atural L anguage G eneration
NLP	N atural L anguage P rocessing
OCR	O ptical C haracter R ecognition
OSM	O pen S treet M ap
POI	P oint O f I nterest

POLY-COR	P olyline C orridor
R-CNN	R egion-based C onvolutional N eural N etwork
ROI	R egion O f I nterest
SEG-COR	S egment C orridor
SRN	S emantic R easoning N etwork
STPA	S patial- T extual P OI A nnotation
TF-IDF	T erm F requency- I nverse D ocument F requency
T-G	T itle- G eo
T-G-I	T itle- G eo- I mage
T-G-I-P	T itle- G eo- I mage- P erspective
T-I	T itle- I mage
UTM	U niversal T ransverse M ercator
ViT	V ision T ransformer
VLMC	V isual- L inguistic M ulti- C lassification
WGS84	W orld G eodetic S ystem 1984

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Leisure walking is an important outdoor activity that offers a wide range of advantages to individuals' psychological, cognitive, and physical well-being [2]. Beyond its health advantages, Ballatore et al. noted that leisure walking is a geographical phenomenon as it connects people with spatial environments and places [3]. Unlike destination-oriented walking, such as commuting to work or school, leisure walkers do not prioritize the shortest or fastest routes. This is because they often do not have a fixed destination. Some leisure walks even start and end at the same location, meaning that the concept of a "shortest path" becomes irrelevant. They often seek routes that offer opportunities to explore both nature and constructed spaces that engage with diverse interests through visits of Points of Interest (POIs) [4]. For instance, many walkers today use guided walk websites and mobile applications to design routes that align with their preferences such as featuring dog-friendly paths, street art routes, or nature trails.

In the context of walking, POIs are defined as specific geographic entities that walkers may find *helpful* or *interesting* along their route [5]. Nature viewpoints, historical landmarks, cultural attractions, local businesses, or even unique architectural features are all considered as POIs if someone finds them useful or attractive [6]. In fact, POIs play a key role in shaping leisure walking experiences. This is because most leisure walkers select and decide on a route based on the POIs they expect to encounter along the way [3, 7]. For instance, a flower lover will choose a different route than a dog lover.

Even if they walk along the same path, the POIs where the flower lover decides to stop may differ from those that attract the dog lover because each is looking for different experiences than the other. This example suggests that the presence, characteristics, and accessibility of POIs impact route selection, motivation to explore further, and overall satisfaction of walkers.

Walkers often seek information such as names, locations, and descriptions of POIs before their walk. While names and locations are generally easy to find, descriptive information is often missing or insufficient especially for less popular locations [8]. The shortage of contextually relevant POI descriptions leads to reduced engagement, missed exploration opportunities, and limited support for route planning. This deficiency is because these POI descriptions are manually crafted, which is a labor-intensive and time-consuming process. Another reason is the continuous and rapid change of emerging POIs with its connected challenges of tracking and updating those descriptions. Finally, manually generated descriptions often lack consistency and may fail to capture the unique spatial and semantic attributes that distinguish each POI [8–10].

Recent advancements in Natural Language Generation (NLG) offer promising opportunities for automatically generating POI descriptions for routes [7, 9, 11]. Methods that integrate multimodal data sources, such as textual reviews [8], spatial attributes [3, 7], street view images [5, 9], and contextual information of neighboring locations [5, 8], have demonstrated potential in generating descriptions that closely mimic human-created content. However, those approaches mainly focus on geographic aspects that are useful for navigation. In addition, many existing POI descriptions are derived from non-walking sources, such as reviews of restaurants, cafés, or tourist attractions, resulting in a lack of relevance to leisure walking contexts. They also fail to reflect different semantic perspectives. For example, descriptions of the same public garden written by a flower lover and a dog owner can differ significantly. While the flower lover may describe seasonal blooms and a colorful atmosphere, the dog owner may focus on aspects like accessibility and open space. In summary, POI descriptions can now be generated automatically, helping to overcome the limitations of manual annotation by providing scalable, up-to-date, and coherent outputs. As leisure walking becomes more popular [12], there is a need to generate POI descriptions that are tailored to walking experiences and reflect diverse user perspectives. Such descriptions not only enhance the usability of digital maps and

navigation tools [7, 8], but also support leisure walkers in planning and exploring their surroundings [3].

1.2 Research Problem

The possibility of automatically producing POI descriptions highlights shortcomings with respect to generating user-perspective-driven POI description with a specific focus on leisure walking. Additionally, while some research has explored multimodal approaches for POI-related tasks such as annotation and generation using text, images, and geographic data, current methods for POI description generation rely only on text and spatial information. So far, no existing model includes visual information when generating POI descriptions.

1.3 Research Aim

This research aims to develop a multimodal framework that integrates user interests, POI imagery, and spatial context to automatically generate POI descriptions tailored to the perspectives of individuals engaged in leisure walks, by leveraging advanced NLP techniques, visual-linguistic models, and contextual embeddings.

1.4 Research Questions and Hypothesis

Question 1: *To what extent does incorporating visual information improve the ability of a model to generate POI descriptions that reflect both the physical and semantic characteristics of a place?*

Photos of POIs often capture rich visual cues, such as setting, appearance, and ambiance, that are difficult to fully convey through text or metadata (category labels, coordinates) alone. This question explores whether visual features can be effectively used to enhance the descriptiveness of automatically generated POI content.

Hypothesis 1: *I hypothesize that POI images integrated as a modality in the model will help the model to better capture the physical attributes and overall atmosphere of a*

place. As a result, the generated descriptions will be better aligned with the POI's visual appearance. For example, a POI image showing a shaded bench under a tree near a quiet lake can provide the model with additional cues about the atmosphere like calm, peaceful, relaxing and visual characteristics such as presence of trees, water reflections, natural shade.

Question 2: *How can a walker's perspective be effectively integrated into a model for generating POI descriptions tailored to leisure walking?*

When people describe POIs for leisure walking, they do not just list facts. They often share how the place made them feel or why they liked it. This perspective is especially important in leisure walking, where the goal is not just to get from point *A* to *B*, but to enjoy the environment along the way. However, most automatic POI description models ignore this human element and only focus on objective details like location or category. To make descriptions more useful and engaging for walkers, it is necessary to find a way to extract this subjective perspective from existing text or data and integrate it into the generation model.

Hypothesis: *Incorporating walkers' personal context into the generation model will produce POI descriptions that enhance semantic diversity and achieve better alignment with reference descriptions in the context of leisure walking.* This hypothesis is based on the observation that the walker's perspective is embedded in human-written POI descriptions through expressions of interest, emotion, or personal experience. In the context of leisure walking, where the journey is guided more by experience than by destination, such perspectives are relevant to the content of the description. It is therefore possible to extract these signals by analyzing the themes, or narrative patterns in existing POI or route descriptions, and use them to guide the generation of personalized content.

1.5 Research Scope

The scope of this project is limited to the task of generating descriptive text for POIs in the context of leisure walks, using multimodal data sources. Specifically, the study focuses on integrating textual, visual, and spatial inputs to improve the quality of automatically generated POI descriptions. The dataset is drawn primarily from WalkingMaps, which provides user-contributed POIs with accompanying titles, descriptions, images,

and geographic coordinates. As WalkingMaps covers walking routes within Victoria and other regions of Australia, the dataset is geographically limited to the Australian context. In addition, all descriptions are written in English, and therefore, the modelling and evaluation are confined to English only.

Data preprocessing and filtering are applied to ensure quality, while the modeling component investigates the effectiveness of incorporating different modality combinations. The evaluation is limited to automatic text generation metrics, including BLEU, CIDEr, and BERTScore, which quantitatively assess the similarity between generated and reference descriptions. Human evaluation or user studies of description quality are beyond the scope of this research.

At the same time, several aspects are beyond the scope of this research. These include broader POI-related tasks such as identification, recommendation, or categorization, as well as user studies or large-scale human evaluation of the generated descriptions.

1.6 Contribution

- **Problem Formulation for Leisure Walks:** This research is the first study to explicitly frame POI description generation in the context of leisure walks. Existing approaches have primarily focused on general-purpose POI datasets, whereas this work emphasizes user-perspective needs for walking experiences.
- **Multimodal Dataset Construction:** The project constructs a multimodal dataset from WalkingMaps that combines POI titles, user-generated descriptions, geographic coordinates, and images. A systematic data analysis and preprocessing pipeline is developed, including filtering uninformative descriptions and resolving POI identity through title and geo-location clustering.
- **Multimodal Modeling Approach:** A novel framework is proposed that integrates textual, visual, and spatial modalities for POI description generation. This extends prior work, which has focused primarily on text and spatial inputs, by investigating the added value of visual data.

1.7 Data and Code Availability

To ensure transparency, reproducibility, and long-term accessibility, all data and implementation code developed in this thesis are publicly available through both institutional and public repositories.

- **GitLab (University of Melbourne):** <https://gitlab.unimelb.edu.au/THIMINHHAIB/poi-description.git>
- **GitHub (Public Mirror):** <https://github.com/rst5018/master-project-poi-description.git>

The dataset used in this study, which integrates Points of Interest (POIs), route-level metadata, images, and contextual information collected from the WalkingMaps platform and enriched with OpenStreetMap (OSM) features, is archived on **Figshare** and accessible via the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.30479810>

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Leisure Walking

Nordh et al. [13] define leisure walking as a non-competitive, non-organized, outdoor physical activity primarily taking place in urban areas. This definition was later adopted and expanded by Ballatore et al. [3], who asserted that leisure walking is an outdoor, non-strenuous activity mainly conducted in rural areas and parks. Sharing a similar viewpoint but articulated differently, Zurawik [14] emphasized that leisure walking provides an escape from routines and daily life, characterizing it as an activity of exploring and observing nature while walking. Despite variations in phrasing, the recreational aspect of leisure walking is consistently highlighted. In other words, leisure walking emphasizes positive experiences during the walk, such as fascination with nature, reflection, and mental relaxation. Unlike hiking and trekking, leisure walking typically takes place over shorter durations and does not require specialized equipment [3]. Furthermore, in contrast to transport walking, where the task is to reach a specific destination, leisure walking typically does not have a pragmatic purpose or endpoint, being instead undertaken for enjoyment, relaxation, and overall well-being. Examples of transport walking include walking to work, school, or the nearest grocery stores, whereas walking around the neighborhood, in a park, or even walking while playing golf are typical examples of walking for leisure [15]. Consequently, leisure walking emphasizes emotional experiences, and the stops made during leisure walking are usually not destinations themselves but rather points that walkers find interesting and from which they wish to explore further.

Historically, the practice of leisure walking aligns closely with broader societal and environmental developments. With cities becoming cultural and touristic hubs, the act of leisure walking gained popularity as a means of exploring, enjoying, and experiencing the surrounding environment. The evolution of leisure walking is closely tied to the development of urban spaces designed to attract visitors through carefully curated walking experiences—examples include thematic routes through historic city centers, culturally enriched districts, or scenic landscapes [16]. Throughout the 20th century and into the 21st century, urban planners and tourism authorities have increasingly recognized leisure walking as a valuable economic and social activity. Cities began leveraging data-driven approaches to enhance the visitor economy, recognizing leisure walks as key contributors to tourism, local economy stimulation, and city branding strategies [17].

First, research focuses on leisure walking because of its implications for public health and individual well-being [14, 18]. Benefits like low-cost, accessible physical activity, building social connections, improving social interaction skills are strongly associated with leisure walking. These benefits explain why leisure walking attracts researchers from health and psychological sectors. Leisure walking has, however, also become a topic of growing interest in geographical research, and the aforementioned benefits cannot fully explain for the trend. To understand it, we must recognize that leisure walking is a geographical phenomenon due to its inherent connection to spatial contexts and places [3]. It is clear that recreational walking occurs within and interacts with specific environments, prompting researchers to investigate the key factors that motivate individuals to walk. This includes studying the geographical characteristics of spaces or walking routes, assessing the walkability of specific areas, evaluating the impact of urban design, understanding the spatial patterns of outdoor activities, and supporting route planning [19]. Therefore, leisure walking serves not only as a personal or health-related activity but as a spatial practice that enables geographers to explore the dynamic interactions between people, place, and the built environment.

2.2 Points of Interest

Descriptions of routes are often structured around a sequence of places people encounter along the way. For navigational purposes, these places are often landmarks that aid

wayfinding [20], whereas, descriptions of leisure-oriented walk focus on POIs that are engaging to walkers and often aligned with their personal interests.

The origin of POIs refers to the marked locations on physical maps [21]. Specifically, cartographers highlighted notable features such as mountain summits or historical battlefields on paper maps. These marked points are considered the early POIs in cartography.

Nowadays, a POI is, at its core, a specific geographic location that someone may find useful or interesting [22]. POIs are no longer represented solely as points; rather, they are more regarded as places of interest that can also take linear or polygonal forms, such as walking trails, park boundaries, or river segments. However, the term POI remains widely used because its concise and simple definition allows for a wide range of interpretations and representations, depending on the context in which it is used, including health, mobility, urban planning, sustainable development, community studies, navigation systems, situational awareness and tourism. The nature and function of POIs vary significantly based on the application domain and the user's intent. To clarify and illustrate these variations, Table 2.1 provides an example of how POIs are represented and utilized across different applications.

TABLE 2.1: Representation and roles of POIs in applications

Application	POI Representation	Roles
Health	Parks, healthy food stores, liquor/-tobacco shops, clinics	Influence physical/mental health by promoting activity or exposing to risks e.g., pollution, stress [23, 24]
Mobility	POIs with time-specific visit patterns e.g., shopping centers, transit hubs	Infer floating population sizes, assist in transport engineering and dynamic mobility analysis [25]
Urban Planning	Public facilities like parks, schools, health clinics	Indicators of accessibility and quality of life; help guide infrastructure planning and resource allocation [26, 27]
Sustainable Development	Public transport stops, green/public spaces	Track progress on Sustainable Development Goals, e.g., equitable access to services, urban inclusivity [21]
Navigation Systems	Landmarks such as gas stations, restaurants, buildings, hotels	Aid in wayfinding, route directions, and trip planning [28]
Situational Recommendations	POIs relevant to user’s current context or need (e.g., boredom, spontaneous plans)	Provide context-aware suggestions via situational recommending systems [29]
Situational Awareness	Target points, unit positions, terrain features e.g., forests, swamps	Enhance operational understanding by identifying critical points in the environment; support decision-making under time constraints. E.g., in mCOP, a military tactical decision support system, POIs are used to estimate objectives, evaluate threat levels [30]
Tourism	Tourist attractions such as museums, monuments, scenic areas	Help travelers explore destinations, plan personalized routes, and improve visitor experiences [3]

For instance, urban planners focus on POIs representing public facilities essential for assessing community well-being, whereas navigation systems emphasize salient landmarks critical for efficient wayfinding [20]. In military situational awareness systems, POIs are

targets for offensive operations or key assets for defense planning. In addition, mobility analyses use POIs to explore spatial dynamics and human behavior, while tourism applications leverage POIs to enrich visitor experiences and personalize leisure routes.

In the specific context of leisure walk, POIs function not merely as navigational aids but as thematic anchors, guiding walkers through routes designed around shared characteristics such as cultural heritage sites, scenic landscapes, or architectural landmarks [17]. The characteristics and enriched information of POIs provide ability to personalize route suggestions and selections, making routes more suitable for individual preferences. This help walkers engage deeply with their environment, enriching their recreational experiences, and providing contextually meaningful narratives [3]. Thus, POIs transform ordinary leisure walks into culturally and emotionally engaging experiences, reinforcing their critical importance within recreational and tourism-focused applications.

2.3 Computational Representation of POIs

POIs are digitally stored with various attributes. The richness of these attributes depend on the data source. At a foundational level, POI datasets include the name and geospatial coordinates (typically stored as point geometries but occasionally as linear or polygonal features defined by latitude and longitude). Beyond these basics, more descriptive properties such as operating hours, contact information, website links and user-generated contents require access to well-maintained and purpose-specific data sources. For instance, while *Overture*¹ provide standardized POI attributes (names, categories, addresses, and coordinates), *Google Places*² offers user-generated contents such as reviews and photos.

POI datasets that offer richer and more descriptive information are more useful for applications and help answer research questions more effectively. For example, while navigation apps may only require a POI's name and coordinates, answering questions such as which factors of a POI attract leisure walkers demands richer data, e.g. user reviews, descriptions or photos associated with the POI.

¹<https://docs.overturemaps.org/guides/places/>

²<https://developers.google.com/maps/documentation/places/web-service>

Historically, POI data was collected manually. However, such approaches struggle to keep pace with the dynamic nature of these POIs’ complex attributes. Today, the integration of geographic technologies, mobile software, and artificial intelligence increasingly drives the automation of POI enrichment tasks. These advances make it possible not only to construct but also to maintain and update POI datasets at scale. Consequently, tasks related to POI datasets (expanding POI sources and enriching POI descriptive contents) have become more feasible and scalable, attracting considerable attention. For more detail, representative tasks involved in the automated processing of POI data is presented in the table below.

TABLE 2.2: Common POI Tasks

Task Name	Description	Examples
POI Extraction/ Identification	Constructing POI datasets by identifying POIs from raw data sources	Extracting POIs from sources like Yahoo or Flickr [22], or identifying POIs from street view images using signboard detection and scene text recognition [9, 10].
POI Annotation	Enriching POI datasets with additional metadata or context information, usually involving human or AI-assisted labeling	Detecting and labeling POIs with contextual information from visual and textual data [5].
User Content Generation	Producing content that mimics or replaces user-generated data such as reviews, ratings, or free-form descriptions	Generating descriptive summaries for POIs using multimodal data for use in recommendation or conversational systems [7, 8].

Table 2.2 highlights the three tasks associated with POI data. Starting with *identification*, this task constructs POIs from raw data source such as geo-tagged photos [22] or street view images [9, 10]. While *POI annotation* enriches existing POIs by inferring more complex attributes such as tags, categories, accessibility or ranks [5], free-form, human-like contents are the result of *user content generation*. Description generation is a representative task of the latter, aiming to produce textual summaries that reflect both factual details and user perspectives. Together, these three tasks enhance the richness

of POI datasets, making them more informative, engaging, and better suited to support complex, user-centered spatial applications.

2.4 Multimodal Learning in POI Tasks

Applications of POIs make them a subject of research. In particular, POI generation, annotation, and user-content generation tasks attract researchers working in AI and spatial computing.

Techniques including deep learning [9], graph-based models [31] and multimodal learning [32] have been applied to address these tasks. Among them, multimodal learning is a promising approach because it integrates information from multiple sources (text, image and coordinates). In contrast, if using only a single modality with deep learning or graph-based models, we may have to choose between spatial features (coordinates), physical features (images) or semantic context (textual descriptions), leading to an inability to fully exploit diverse facets of POIs. This section will focus on what multimodal learning is, why it aligns with POI-related tasks, and how recent studies have put it into practice.

“Modality refers to the way in which something happens or is experienced” [33], commonly aligning with human sensory modalities such as vision, sound, or touch. Technically, the term modality represents a form of input data such as images, text, audio, or sensor inputs, and multimodal learning refers to building models that can jointly process and reason across such diverse data types. This definition highlights how a modality is closely tied to how humans perceive and interact with their environment. Human perception is naturally multimodal. For example, we unlikely use solely one sense when walking outdoors. We use our eyes, ears, nose and all other senses to understand our surroundings at the same time. This natural capacity for multimodal perception has inspired the development of multimodal learning [33]. I next present a summary of the main strengths and weaknesses of multimodal learning, and then explore some recent research on multimodal approaches for POIs.

Models with multiple input modalities are generally better at learning from data, even in situations where some information is missing [33] because each modality offers complementary information. What is missing or ambiguous in one can often be clarified

by another. For example, combining street view images with POI descriptions improves location classification by resolving visual or textual uncertainty. This makes multimodal models more robust in case of real-world applications where data may be missing or unreliable [34]. Another key strength of multimodal learning is that it supports cross-modal reasoning [35], which allows multimodal models to connect information from various sources and reason like humans. A multimodal model can combine textual reviews of walking trails, user preferences, and scenic images of the surroundings to suggest a walking route that is personalized and for individuals [36, 37]. Such models produce results that are closer to human perception because they mimic the way humans perceive the world [35]. As such, multimodal learning not only enhances technical performance, but also brings AI closer to the richness of human experiences, making it a powerful paradigm in modern machine learning [33].

These benefits come however at the cost of increased computational complexity and data integration difficulties. Aligning diverse data types requires sophisticated architectures and large-scale, annotated datasets. Furthermore, missing modality problems and imbalanced input coverage can degrade model reliability, especially during inference [34]. Lastly, interpretability remains a critical limitation, as the internal reasoning processes across modalities are often difficult to trace [35].

Multimodal learning has attracted increasing attention in both research and practical applications [38]. In the geographical domain, data is inherently heterogeneous, involving images, textual descriptions, and sensor readings [39]. Consequently, multimodal approaches have proven to be particularly effective for tasks such as route recommendation, geographic knowledge extraction, POI annotation, where relying on a single modality often results in incomplete or biased representations of spatial environments [5, 40]. This review focuses on tasks that contribute to the creation and enrichment of POI data, including POI identification, semantic annotation, and textual description generation. Particularly, seven studies are published between 2019 and 2024. These works differ in their task objectives, data modalities, model architectures, and application scenarios. Table 2.3 presents the types of data modalities commonly integrated in these tasks and summarizes the modalities employed in each study, highlighting the integration of text, image, and spatial data.

TABLE 2.3: Multi-modal learning studies

Paper	Task	Spatial		
		Text	Map data	Image
Zhang et al.(2022) [9]	POI identification	✓	✗	✓
Chen et al.(2024) [10]	POI identification	✓	✓	✓
Noorian et al.(2019) [32]	POI annotation	✓	✗	✓
Zhang et al.(2023) [41]	POI annotation	✓	✓	✗
Zhang et al.(2024) [5]	POI annotation	✓	✓	✓
Zhou et al.(2021) [8]	Description generation	✓	✓	✗
Liu et al.(2023) [1]	Description generation	✓	✓	✗

Table 2.3 shows how textual features are utilized in all seven approaches. The concept of textual data in these works is broad and encompasses several forms such as POI names, user reviews, OCR text. Specifically, Zhang and colleagues [5, 41] utilize POI names as the primary textual input to address the POI annotation task. Their approach demonstrates how even minimal textual information can support semantic labeling of POIs. Longer and richer semantic textual content such as user reviews is used in POI description generation tasks [1, 8]. These reviews often contain detailed narratives about user experiences, services, and other contextual factors, making them a valuable source for generating personalized and informative descriptions. Additionally, scene text, typically extracted from street view images via OCR, is widely leveraged in POI identification and classification tasks. This form of textual data often appears on storefronts, signboards, or building facades, and includes valuable information such as business names, service types, or brand logos. It acts as a bridge between image and textual modalities, enriching the semantic understanding of POI environments.

In the reviewed studies, image and spatial data are both optional modalities. Specifically, four out of seven papers incorporate image data, while five utilize spatial modalities. In all instances where imagery is utilized, the source is street view images; however, spatial data can take various forms, including geographic coordinates, spatial proximity, and information about surrounding POIs. The main purposes of the two kinds of modalities (visual and spatial) can be capturing the appearance of POIs, extracting sign text, estimating POI locations, and providing environmental context such as nearby infrastructure. Among spatial features, coordinates are the most commonly used. A case in

point is Chen et al. [10], who employ coordinates to estimate precise POI locations from multi-view images, or Zhang et al. [5, 41], leveraging them and nearby POIs to provide contextual information to enhance POI annotation.

Apart from modalities, these studies vary in their modeling structure, the way they fuse multi-modalities and the methods of evaluation, which leads to different outcomes. Example of Zhang et al. [9] propose a three-stage framework consisting of segmenting regions of interest (ROIs) related to POIs using Cascade Mask R-CNN with a Swin-Transformer backbone, recognizing text within the ROIs using Differentiable Binarization (DB) for detection and Semantic Reasoning Network (SRN) for recognition; and finally, classifying both the ROIs and text lines using a Visual-Linguistic Multi-Classification (VLMC) model. While Chen et al. [10] also begin with detecting signboards using the same model as Zhang et al., they use PaddleOCR for text recognition and Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network (CRNN) for recognition. A key difference is that whereas Zhang et al. [9] use BERT for multimodal classification, Chen et al. [10] feature a Large Language Model (LLM) for generating POI names and incorporates geographic information for spatial localization. By employing more complex models and fully integrating all three modalities, Chen et al. achieve a higher recall rate (59% compared to Zhang et al.'s 53% F1-score on their POI-generated dataset) and explicitly report the average distance error.

ST-Sem [32] is one of the earliest representatives of semantic annotation. With street-level imagery as input, two modalities are generated: One modality is the image itself, which is passed through ResNet for classification based on common visual characteristics of each POI type's facade. The other modality is scene text, detected directly from the input image using TextBoxes++; these detected texts are then classified based on cosine similarity with predefined POI category labels. Finally, the classification results from the two modality channels are fused using Linear Bimodal Fusion(LBF).

Two other representative models for annotation task are Spatial-Textual POI annotation (STPA) [41] and Multimodal modal for POI Semantic Annotation (M3PA) [5], both proposed by Zhang et al. Although both models have a common architectural pattern, with encoding different aspects of POI information following by fusing the encoding, and then performing classification based on the fused data, in each stage, they are different in the methods and algorithms used. Particularly, in encoding phase, STPA utilizes a

GCN-based spatial encoder to capture spatial correlations from POI geographic locations and an attention-based text encoder to process POI names, while M3PA uses a pre-trained and fine-tuned ResNet [42] as an image encoder for street view images, a geographic attention mechanism for aggregating visual context from nearby POIs, and GeoBERT [5], a spatially enhanced version of BERT, for encoding POI names along with their spatial relationships. In addition, STPA applies a multi-view fusion approach, whereas M3PA employs a dedicated fusion model tailored to handle visual, textual, and spatial representations. Finally, both models are evaluated on the AMap dataset³, a large-scale POI dataset derived from the Gaode Map platform (a China’s major digital mapping service). The dataset includes two representative subsets, Haidian and Lixia, corresponding to urban districts in Beijing and Jinan, respectively. These subsets capture distinct spatial characteristics, with Haidian representing a dense metropolitan area and Lixia a medium-sized urban district. M3PA generally demonstrated superior performance compared to STPA. The following charts illustrate the comparison across three key metrics: Accuracy, Macro-F1 [43], and Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) of the two models.

FIGURE 2.1: Performance comparison of STPA and M3PA on Haidian and Lixia subsets of AMap dataset

The results in Figure 2.1 indicate that M3PA achieves more accurate and robust semantic annotations, making it better suited for POI understanding tasks. This improvement is due to its multimodal design, especially the integration of street view images and spatial textual modeling via GeoBERT.

Finally, consider the two representative models of POI description generation, Multi-Modal Description Generator (MMDG) [8] and Guide-Select Generative Model (GSGM) [1],

³<https://lbs.amap.com/api/webservice/guide/api/search/>

both based on an encoder-decoder architecture. In the encoding phase, both models process three types of information: user reviews, POI category, and geographical context. MMDG concatenates all user reviews into a single sequence and encodes it using a Transformer, while GSGM encodes each review independently by using BERT, enabling finer-grained semantic representation. With respect to POI categories, MMDG applies a simple one-hot encoding, a less expressive method, whereas GSGM utilizes BERT again to capture richer semantic features from the category text. A highlight of MMDG is the Context-Aware Convolutional Neural Network (CACNN), which is used to encode spatial information. In detail, Zhou et al. [8] construct a context tensor based on surrounding POIs and applies CACNN to extract features from this tensor, effectively capturing spatial dependencies and enriching the generated descriptions with contextual signals. Meanwhile, GSGM takes a different route by directly encoding the latitude and longitude of POIs using a Transformer-based spatial encoder.

Liu et al. [1] enhance their model with a fusion strategy. Specifically, while MMDG simply uses a linear function to integrate the modalities, GSGM leverages a more advanced and effective Guide-Select fusion mechanism. Structurally, this mechanism includes a Transformer-based guider that aggregates global information across input modalities and a selector embedded within the GPT-2 decoder layers, which dynamically fuses inputs using attention based on the current decoding context. As a result of architectural improvements, particularly in its fusion mechanism, GSGM outperforms the MMDG across most evaluation metrics [1], especially in terms of content diversity and semantic richness. For example, GSGM achieves a BLEU-1 [44] score of 61.2, slightly higher than 60.6 for MMDG.

Interestingly, for both POI identification and annotation, there are studies that successfully combine all three modalities: text, image, and spatial data. In these cases, the integration leads to notable performance improvements. For instance, a three-stage POI identification framework [9], which combines street view images, scene text extracted via OCR, and geographic coordinates, achieves an F1-score of 53%, and is shown to outperform text-only or image-only variants. In addition, the M3PA model [5], which fuses textual, visual, and spatial features, outperforms STPA that utilizes only text and spatial information. These results highlight that incorporating image data alongside text and spatial features leads to more accurate POI understanding. However, the description generation task has not yet explored the use of image data. As a result, no existing

study has investigated the effect of combining all three modalities in this context.

2.5 Research Gap

Through the literature review, I identified that firstly, the proposed solutions do not specifically serve the purpose of leisure walks. This is evident through the datasets used and the models that have been developed. Specifically, although the datasets contain many POIs with diverse categories, including those related to outdoor spaces, they were not collected specifically for the purpose of leisure walking. In all models developed to address POI tasks, and especially in description generation, none of the models include contextual information about leisure walks or show any relevance to user perspective or walker opinion. In addition, combining textual, visual, and spatial modalities often leads to better performance. In both POI identification and annotation, several models have successfully integrated all three types of data [5, 10]. However, POI description generation is an exception. Despite advances in modeling text and spatial information, current methods have not incorporated visual data yet.

Accordingly, **the lack of attention to the leisure walking context and visual modality in POI description generation** presents an opportunity for this research.

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Data

3.1.1 Sources of Data

Section 2.3 mentions that POI datasets typically contain POIs with a variety of attributes, ranging from basic information (name, category, address, and coordinates, to richer and descriptive features including reviews, descriptions, and photos). In practice, these attributes are gathered and enriched from three main types of data sources:

- **Community-based digital maps:** OSM¹, Google Maps² and Baidu³ are three representative examples. This type of source mainly provides basic features. A major advantage of these sources is their ability to provide a large number of POIs with detailed geographic information, such as coordinates and geometry, as well as semantic attributes (name, address, tags and, types that describe the function or category of each place). Therefore, POIs collected from these sources have been widely used in various studies related to health [24], urban planning [27], sustainable development [21], and navigation [28].

¹<https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

²<https://www.google.com/maps>

³<https://map.baidu.com/>

- **Commercial platforms:** Examples of this type include TripAdvisor⁴, Yelp⁵ and Booking.com⁶. These platforms enrich POI datasets with user-contributed information such as reviews and ratings. Such data are mainly used in applications related to tourism and service industries [3].
- **Activity-focused platforms:** Although these platforms provide fewer POIs compared to community-based mapping services, they offer rich contextual information such as route difficulty, terrain features, elevation profiles, user-contributed photos, and narrative descriptions of walking, hiking, cycling, or camping experiences. Slow Ways⁷, Rankers⁸, Wikiloc⁹, Walking Maps¹⁰ are representative platforms of this type. Information collected from such sources is typically used in specific contexts, such as leisure walking or outdoor activity analysis. However, relatively few studies have collected and utilized such contextual data for POI-related research. A recent example is the work by Hamzei et al. [45], who built a POI dataset by collecting over 4,000 POIs directly related to leisure walking from the Walking Maps platform and enriching it by matching these POIs with corresponding entries in OSM.

The present research, given its focus on the context of leisure walking, starts with activity-focused data sources to collect POIs that have been created and identified by walkers. The dataset will then be enriched with additional geographical context information from community-based digital maps. The specific data sources used in this study are described in detail below.

WalkingMaps Platform

WalkingMaps is a publicly accessible platform developed by Victoria Walks Inc., a non-profit organization dedicated to promoting walkable communities across Australia. Unlike general-purpose mapping services such as OpenStreetMap (OSM) or Google Maps,

⁴<https://www.tripadvisor.com/>

⁵<https://www.yelp.com/>

⁶<https://www.booking.com/>

⁷<https://beta.slowways.org/>

⁸<https://www.rankers.co.nz/>

⁹<https://www.wikiloc.com/>

¹⁰<https://walkingmaps.com.au/>

which typically focus on urban infrastructure or navigation, WalkingMaps is specifically designed to support leisure walking. This focus makes it particularly suitable for research that aims to understand and model walking experiences.

There are several reasons why WalkingMaps was selected as the primary data source for this study:

- **Direct alignment with leisure walking context:** All routes and POIs on WalkingMaps are created for recreational walking. This ensures that the data inherently reflects the context of leisure walking, unlike other sources where POIs are often oriented toward driving, commuting, or tourism. As a result, the dataset is directly aligned with the research objective of generating POI descriptions tailored to walkers' interests and experiences.
- **POI descriptions reflecting walker perspectives:** The platform encourages users to contribute narrative descriptions of places they encounter along the routes. These descriptions are typically subjective, experience-driven, and often include emotional or evaluative content (e.g., quiet atmosphere, scenic view, dog-friendly environment). Such characteristics are essential for training a model that aims to generate perspective-rich descriptions of POIs. In this study, they are treated as ground truth reference texts.
- **Availability of multimodal and thematic information:** In addition to textual descriptions, WalkingMaps provides other useful modalities such as geographic coordinates and images of POIs, allowing the integration of visual and spatial features into multimodal learning models. Furthermore, each walking route is categorized under thematic tags such as nature walk, dog-friendly, or kid-friendly, which can be used to extract high-level context and represent the perspectives or preferences of walkers.

As illustrated in Figure 3.1, the platform offers interactive maps displaying walking routes and associated POIs. Each POI includes one or more photos, GPS coordinates, and detailed descriptions. These features collectively make WalkingMaps a rich, relevant, and context-aware data source for building and evaluating models that generate POI descriptions from a walker's perspective.

FIGURE 3.1: Illustration of walking routes and POI details on the Walking Maps platform

OSM

While the WalkingMaps platform provides POIs selected and described by walkers, it does not include detailed information about the geographical environment in which these POIs are placed. However, the description of a POI—particularly in the context of leisure walking—is often influenced by its surrounding geographical features. For example, the presence of a nearby river, park, or urban infrastructure can significantly affect how a place is perceived and described. Since WalkingMaps lacks this contextual information, it is necessary to enrich POIs with additional spatial attributes obtained from community-based digital maps. For this purpose, OSM has selected as a complementary data source.

OSM is a collaborative mapping platform that offers detailed and structured geospatial data contributed by a global community of volunteers. OSM also underpins various mapping services, including Google Maps and Bing Maps¹¹. It is widely used in geospatial research and urban computing due to its openness, flexibility, and rich semantic tagging system. For instance, Muroñ et al. [7] gathered spatial features and hierarchical relationships relevant to each POI from OSM as their primary data source for generating descriptions for places by using Overpass API. In addition, both Shi et al. [46] and Zhang et al. [9] integrated OSM road networks into their AI models for geographical reasoning tasks, while Chen et al. [10] employed OSM as a supplementary data source to enrich the semantic context of their primary data.

¹¹<https://www.bing.com/maps>

In this study, OSM is used to extract the environmental context surrounding each POI, which is then incorporated into the model as an independent modality to support the description generation process.

3.1.2 Collection Method

Crawling WalkingMaps Data

To collect structured data from the WalkingMaps platform, a custom web scraper was developed in Python using the `requests`¹² and `BeautifulSoup`¹³ libraries. The WalkingMaps website is organized around individual walking routes, each hosted on a dedicated page accessible via a unique walk ID. Leveraging this structure, the scraper iteratively queried walking route pages by incrementing the walk ID from 1 to 9999. For each valid walk page, the scraper extracts the following metadata:

- **General route information:** name, address, author, and full-text description.
- **Route metrics:** walking time, distance, and difficulty level.
- **Route features:** semantic tags such as “*Dog off-leash area*”, “*Picnic spot*”, or “*Art and culture*”, which provide thematic context.
- **POIs:** a list of manually added POIs along the route, each including title, latitude, longitude, a narrative summary, and an associated image. POI images are downloaded using the predictable URL schema of Walking Maps inferred from HTML input fields.

The collected data is stored in the structured JSON format, with all POI images saved to a local directory for further processing. Error handling and request throttling (1.5-3.0 seconds between requests) are incorporated to ensure stable scraping and prevent server overload. Additionally, walk IDs without accessible content are logged for exclusion.

This approach allows us to collect rich information about available POIs beyond basic metadata such as title and geographic coordinates. Each POI is accompanied by user-generated descriptions and images, offering insight into both the physical characteristics

¹²<https://pypi.org/project/requests/>

¹³<https://beautiful-soup-4.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

and subjective impressions of the place. Additionally, route features reflect contributing user interests, which can be leveraged to infer user perspectives. As a result, the collected data includes textual descriptions, spatial attributes, and visual content, making the dataset well-suited for training and evaluating multimodal AI models aimed at POI description generation.

Enriching POIs with OSM

To enrich information of POIs, this study utilizes the Overpass API to retrieve nearby geographic features from OSM. This study adopts two strategies: (1) a **radius-based** approach that follows prior research [1, 8], and (2) a **route-based** approach that is proposed in this work to better align with the leisure walking context. The details of each method are presented below.

Density-aware Radius-based Surrounding Area For each POI collected from WalkingMaps, a spatial query is performed to extract OSM elements located in the surrounding area. Previous studies such as Liu et al. [1] adopted a broader 2000-meter radius because their POIs primarily consisted of restaurants and service-related venues, for which visitors are often willing to travel longer distances for specific destinations of interest. In this research, I initially considered a 1000-meter radius as a suitable threshold for modeling walking behavior. A 1000-meter radius is supported by behavioral research which shows that the average walking trip distance is approximately 1000 meters [47]. Additionally, it also lies between the commonly cited 400-meter “pedestrian shed” for 5-minute walking intervals [48] and longer leisure walking trip durations, which often range around 12 minutes [49].

However, the analysis of retrieved data revealed that applying a fixed 1000-meter radius leads to substantial imbalance in the number of retrieved nearby features across different POIs. While over 10% of POIs had no nearby elements within this radius, some had more than a thousand, particularly in dense urban environments. This disparity reflects the uneven spatial distribution of POIs across areas with varying population densities.

To address this issue, a density-aware radius selection strategy was implemented. Specifically, smaller radii are used for POIs located in urban areas, where a wide radius may capture excessive and rapidly changing features, resulting in noise rather than useful

context. In these settings, a smaller radius, such as 100 or 200 meters, emphasizes visual visibility and the immediate surroundings, which aligns more closely with how walkers perceive and interact with dense environments. In contrast, for rural or less populated areas, a larger radius such as 1000 meters remains appropriate to ensure a sufficient number of nearby elements are retrieved and to better reflect typical leisure walking distances [49]. This approach balances the spatial context provided for each POI, enabling a more representative and location-sensitive enrichment of geographic features.

To implement variable radii for contextual enrichment, it is essential to determine the population density level of each POI’s surrounding area. For this purpose, I utilize data from the Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS)¹⁴, specifically the Section of State (SOS) dataset [50]. This dataset segments Australia into four distinct levels of population concentration, which serve as the basis for dynamically adjusting the contextual radius based on regional density. The classification levels are shown in Table 3.1.

TABLE 3.1: Classification of Urban and Rural Levels and Assigned Contextual Radius

Name	Definition	Urban or Rural	Radius (m)
Major Urban	Major Urban represents a combination of all Urban Centres with a population of 100,000 or more.	Urban	100
Other Urban	Other Urban represents a combination of all Urban Centres with a population less than or equal to 99,999.	Urban	200
Bounded Locality	Bounded Localities represent a combination of all Localities.	Rural	500
Rural Balance	Rural Balance represents the Remainder of State/Territory.	Rural	1000

This fine-grained classification enables the contextual radius to be scaled appropriately with the level of urbanization, providing a more nuanced understanding of each POI’s spatial setting. As such, the SOS dataset forms a more suitable foundation for density-aware contextual modeling in this study than approaches that rely solely on fixed distance heuristics.

¹⁴<https://www.abs.gov.au/>

Route-based Surrounding Area Unlike the radius-based method, where the surrounding area is defined as a circle around the POI, the route-based approach makes use of the walking route itself. In this study, the surrounding area is defined as a corridor bounded by the previous and next POIs along the route. This corridor captures the immediate spatial environment that a walker would actually encounter while following the path. Two variants of corridor construction are implemented.

- **Segment Corridor:** The centerline is defined as the straight line connecting the previous and next POIs, excluding the current POI from the centerline construction. The corridor is then generated as a rectangular buffer around this line.
- **Polyline Corridor:** The centerline is defined as a polyline passing through three points: previous POI → current POI → next POI. The corridor is then built along this bent centerline, explicitly incorporating the current POI as part of the route.

(a) Segment Corridor

(b) Polyline Corridor

FIGURE 3.2: Corridor construction methods for a POI.

The segment corridor uses a straight line between the previous and next POIs, while the polyline corridor incorporates the current POI.

Both corridor types are constructed by buffering the centerline by $w=100$ m on each side, representing a walking corridor that extends 100 m to the left and right of the path.

For metric accuracy, the centerlines are first projected from WGS84 (latitude-longitude) into the local UTM zone of the study area, ensuring that the 100 m buffer corresponds to an actual ground distance. The resulting corridor polygons are then transformed back to WGS84 coordinates and used in Overpass API queries to extract OSM objects located within these areas.

Selected OSM features In designing the Overpass queries, the focus is placed on OSM features that are commonly relevant to leisure walking contexts. Specifically, the following tags are selected:

- *amenity*: This includes useful public facilities such as benches, drinking fountains, toilets, or picnic tables that support rest and social interaction along walking routes.
- *leisure*: Covers features like parks, playgrounds, or sports grounds that align with recreational walking interests.
- *tourism*: Encompasses landmarks, viewpoints, and cultural attractions that walkers may find interesting or worth visiting.
- *historic*: Captures historical sites or monuments, which often appear in POI descriptions and contribute to the semantic richness of the environment.
- *shop*: Refers to nearby retail places such as cafes, local stores, or kiosks, which may also serve as reference points or resting spots.

For each POI, only OSM elements with a valid type and a point geometry are retained. The extracted nearby POIs are represented as simplified tuples of $[type, location]$ to be later integrated into the model input.

Collected Results

The raw dataset comprises structured walking route data crawled from the WalkingMaps platform and nearby geographic features retrieved from OpenStreetMap (OSM). Table 3.2 summarizes the key statistics of the collected dataset before any filtering or preprocessing.

TABLE 3.2: Summary of Raw Data Collected from WalkingMaps

Route-Level Statistics	
Total walk IDs queried	9,999
Valid walking routes retrieved	2,066
Routes with associated features	1,909
Unique route features identified	15
Most frequent route feature	Seating available
POI-Level Statistics	
Total POIs extracted	19,920
Average POIs per route	10
Maximum POIs in a single route	92
Unique POI titles	16,257
Most common POI title	Playground
POIs with user-generated descriptions	99.98%
Median description length	110 words
Maximum description length	220 words
POIs with attached images	84.81%
Contextual Enrichment	
POIs with radius-based surrounding area	72.25%
POIs with segment corridor	92.90%
POIs with polyline corridor	93.73%

Out of nearly 10,000 walk IDs queried, approximately 2,000 valid walking routes and nearly 20,000 POIs are successfully retrieved. These POIs are diverse, covering more than 16,000 unique titles, with “Playground” being the most common. Most POIs include user-generated descriptions with a median length of 110 words, and around 85% are accompanied by user-uploaded images.

For contextual enrichment, two complementary strategies were applied. The radius-based method enriched about 72% of POIs, while the newly introduced route-based corridor method achieved much broader coverage, with over 90% of POIs assigned contextual corridors.

Overall, the enriched raw dataset therefore provides a strong and context-aware foundation for subsequent filtering, preprocessing, and modeling.

3.1.3 Data Filtering

After collecting the raw data, the first step is to retain only high-quality entries for model training. The dataset may contain noisy or incomplete records, such as very short or duplicated descriptions, missing modalities, or multiple references to the same place. If left unfiltered, these issues could introduce bias, weaken training signals, and reduce model performance. To address this, a filtering stage is applied before preprocessing. The specific procedures are presented in the following subsections.

Description-based Filtering

A statistical analysis was conducted on the POI descriptions from the WalkingMaps dataset to assess their quality and distribution. The key descriptive statistics are summarized in Table 3.3.

It can be seen that out of 19,920 POIs, 19,915 (99.98%) contain at least one description, leaving only five entries without any textual content. 588 descriptions (2.95%) are exact matches to the POI title, indicating that a small fraction of entries provide no additional information beyond the name itself. Furthermore, 527 descriptions contain non-ASCII characters such as accented letters or emojis, and one entry includes HTML tags. These

TABLE 3.3: Summary statistics of POI descriptions

Metric	Value
POIs with description	19,915 (99.98%)
Mean length (characters)	111.58
Median length (characters)	109
Min length (characters)	0
Max length (characters)	219
Exact-match with title	588 (2.95%)
Contains non-ASCII characters	527
Contains HTML tags	1

statistics indicate that the vast majority of descriptions consist of plain, meaningful text, making the dataset well-suited for use in training POI description generation models.

After normalizing whitespace and measuring the length of each description, the resulting distribution and variability are illustrated in Figure 3.3.

FIGURE 3.3: Distribution of POI description lengths (by characters)

Most descriptions range between 80 and 180 characters, while a small group of entries fall below 30 characters. The median length is 109 characters, the interquartile range spans approximately 65–165 characters, and a few outliers reach over 200 characters.

In the filtering step, POIs without any description are removed from the dataset. Given that they account for only five entries (0.02%), their exclusion does not affect the overall

data coverage. From a content quality perspective, descriptions shorter than 30 characters are also discarded, as they typically consist of minimal or repetitive text that adds little to no semantic value. In addition, descriptions that exactly match the POI title are removed because they do not contain any supplementary descriptive information and can act as noise in model training. Together, these filtering criteria led to the removal of approximately 10% of all POIs. This proportion is considered acceptable in practice, as it strikes a balance between ensuring data quality and retaining sufficient training examples for model learning.

Missing Data Filtering

In addition to textual quality checks, the dataset also contains POIs with missing information. Particularly, out of 19,920 POIs, around 85% have valid images. Because images are an input modality in the multimodal framework, POIs without valid images are excluded from the dataset. Although the removal of approximately 15% of POIs due to missing images may appear substantial, this is considered acceptable in multimodal learning tasks. Images represent a core modality that cannot be meaningfully imputed, and excluding such entries avoids introducing noise or bias. Importantly, the remaining 16,895 POIs still constitute a sufficiently diverse dataset for training and evaluation.

Another case concerns walking features, which are missing for 897 POIs (4.5%). Although these features are not used as a direct modality, they provide the basis for extracting walkers' perspectives; without them, the semantic context of the POI cannot be reconstructed. For these reasons, POIs without images or with missing walking features are removed from the dataset, ensuring that all retained entries include the essential information required for both multimodal modeling and perspective-aware description generation.

Title and Geo-location Clustering for POI Identity Resolution

In the WalkingMaps dataset, the same physical POI can be recorded multiple times by different users. Each user may provide a unique description, emphasizing personal impressions, experiences, or perspectives. Rather than treating these as duplicates to be removed, these alternative descriptions represent valuable training material for modeling

walker perspectives. However, a key challenge is that records referring to the same POI are not straightforward to identify.

This difficulty arises from the nature of user-generated content. First, the names of POIs often exhibit variations in spelling, abbreviations, or formatting. For instance, the same park may appear as “St Helen’s Park”, “St Helens Park”, or “St Helens park.” Second, the coordinates provided by users are rarely identical, since they may geotag the place from slightly different standing points around the same location. As a result, records that refer to the same physical entity may appear different in both name and location, making naive matching by string equality or exact coordinates insufficient.

To address this issue, a clustering-based method for POI identity resolution has developed. Instead of relying on a single matching criterion, the method integrates three complementary similarity measures:

- **Fuzzy String Similarity.** This metric evaluates character-level similarity between POI names using the *Levenshtein edit distance* [51]. The edit distance $d_{\text{edit}}(s_1, s_2)$ is the minimum number of insertions, deletions, or substitutions needed to transform string s_1 into string s_2 . The normalized similarity ratio is:

$$\text{FuzzSim}(s_1, s_2) = 1 - \frac{d_{\text{edit}}(s_1, s_2)}{\max(|s_1|, |s_2|)}$$

The score ranges from 0 (completely different) to 1 (identical). This method is effective at handling typos, abbreviations, and formatting inconsistencies (e.g., “*St. Helen’s Park*” vs. “*Saint Helen Park*”), but cannot capture semantic equivalence (e.g., “*Park*” vs. “*Garden*”).

- **Semantic Similarity.** To capture meaning beyond surface-level text, POI names are embedded into 384-dimensional vectors using the pre-trained SentenceTransformer model (`paraphrase-MiniLM-L6-v2`), which follows the *Sentence-BERT* architecture [52]. The similarity between two embeddings u and v is measured using cosine similarity:

$$\text{SemSim}(u, v) = \frac{u \cdot v}{\|u\| \|v\|}$$

The score lies in $[-1, 1]$, with values closer to 1 indicating stronger semantic similarity. This approach captures synonyms (“*Street*” vs. “*Road*”), paraphrases (“*City Hall*” vs. “*Municipal Building*”), and contextual variants. While more computationally expensive than string matching, prior work shows that embeddings substantially improve accuracy in POI matching tasks [53].

- **Geographic Distance.** Finally, spatial proximity ensures that textually similar names refer to colocated places. The *Haversine formula* [54] computes the great-circle distance between two latitude-longitude points (φ_1, λ_1) and (φ_2, λ_2) :

$$d = 2R \cdot \arcsin \left(\sqrt{\sin^2 \left(\frac{\varphi_2 - \varphi_1}{2} \right) + \cos(\varphi_1) \cos(\varphi_2) \sin^2 \left(\frac{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1}{2} \right)} \right)$$

where R is the Earth’s radius, φ denotes latitude, and λ longitude. Distances are expressed in meters.

The identification of these three similarity scores serves as the foundation for designing the clustering workflow. The complete process is illustrated in Figure 3.4.

FIGURE 3.4: Workflow for POI similarity calculation and clustering

As shown in the diagram, the POI titles are first normalized to remove inconsistencies in spelling, casing, and formatting. These normalized titles are then encoded into dense vector representations using a SentenceTransformer model. Once the embeddings are obtained, three types of similarity scores are calculated, and then thresholds are applied to filter POI pairs that are most likely to refer to the same physical place.

In this study, two main thresholds are adopted. First, for textual similarity, a pair of POIs is retained if either the fuzzy string similarity or the semantic similarity exceeded 0.9. This high threshold is selected to prioritize precision and is consistent with previous work showing that similarity cutoffs at or above 0.9 substantially improve the accuracy of POI matching tasks [53]. Second, for spatial proximity, only POI pairs within 100 m of each other are considered. This distance threshold reflects the small positional variations common in user-generated data. Importantly, it also addresses the problem of generic titles such as “*Bench*”, “*Toilets*”, or “*Park*”, which may appear across different suburbs but should not be clustered together without geographic constraints.

The candidate pairs passing these thresholds are used to construct an undirected graph, where POIs are represented as nodes and edges denote similarity relations. Clusters are then extracted as connected components, which naturally support transitive merging: if POI *A* matches POI *B* and POI *B* matches POI *C*, then all three belong to the same cluster. This process consolidates multiple records of the same physical place while retaining the diverse user-generated descriptions associated with it, which are later leveraged for perspective-aware description generation.

After applying this procedure to the WalkingMaps dataset, a total of **848 clusters** are formed from **2,502** non-unique POIs. The cluster size distribution, summarized in Table 3.4, shows that clusters contained on average about three POIs, with a median of two. This indicates that most clusters consist of only a small number of POIs, typically pairs or triplets. The distribution, however, is skewed by a few large clusters, with the largest cluster containing **53** POIs.

While these statistics provide a quantitative overview of clustering outcomes, it is also instructive to examine individual clusters in detail. Figure 3.5 illustrates a typical case where POIs share the same title but differ in their descriptions, reflecting multiple perspectives of the same place.

TABLE 3.4: Descriptive statistics of cluster sizes

Metric	Cluster size
Count	848
Mean	2.95
Std	3.94
Min	2
25%	2
50% (Median)	2
75%	2
Max	53

POI Cluster #4 – 2 POIs

St Kilda Sea Baths

You can stop for a swim, spa or seaweed wrap here or grab a bite to eat in one of the cafes or restaurants based here.

St Kilda Sea Baths

Dating back to mid 19th Century, located on St Kilda Beach near St Kilda Pier. It's a St Kilda institution & forms part of Melbourne's rich beach-side history; an intrinsic part of Melbourne culture

FIGURE 3.5: Example cluster with two POIs titled *St Kilda Sea Baths*. While the names are identical, the descriptions reflect different perspectives of different contributors: one focused on leisure activities and another on historical and cultural value.

Another example is the largest cluster, which contains **53** POIs all referring to *St Helen's Park*. Although the titles vary slightly in spelling and formatting (e.g., “St Helens Park”, “St Helen’s Park”), they correspond to the same physical location. Because this park covers a relatively large area, the associated images capture different points, and the descriptions emphasize diverse aspects: playgrounds and schools, well-maintained

footpaths, public art, or the park’s suitability for late-night walks. A selection of descriptions and images from this cluster is shown in Figure 3.6.

FIGURE 3.6: Example cluster with 53 POIs all referring to *St Helen's Park*. Although the titles vary slightly in spelling and formatting, the images capture different vantage points and the descriptions emphasize diverse perspectives.

Together, the statistical overview and the two case studies illustrate the effectiveness of the clustering procedure. It consolidates redundant entries into unified POI identities, while at the same time preserving multi-perspective descriptions that enrich the dataset for subsequent perspective-aware modeling tasks.

Data Splitting

After filtering, the final dataset consists of 14,648 POIs, including 1,275 clustered POIs and 14,013 independent POIs. Both groups are preserved because clustered POIs capture multi-perspective descriptions of the same physical place, while independent POIs

contribute unique and diverse examples.

To enable balanced and reproducible evaluation, the dataset is divided into ten folds. The splitting strategy is designed to ensure that clusters remain intact within a single fold, while independent POIs are evenly distributed by count. This prevents information leakage between training and testing sets and maintains a representative balance of clustered and independent examples in each fold.

Table 3.5 summarizes the distribution of clustered and independent POIs across the ten folds. Each fold is stored in two files: one for clustered POIs (`cluster_X.csv`) and one for independent POIs (`pois_X.csv`). For example, Fold 1 contains 122 clustered POIs and 1,402 independent POIs, while Fold 5 contains 145 clustered POIs and 1,401 independent POIs.

TABLE 3.5: Distribution of clustered and independent POIs across folds

Fold	Clustered POIs	Independent POIs
1	122	1402
2	113	1402
3	128	1402
4	113	1401
5	145	1401
6	139	1401
7	143	1401
8	121	1401
9	136	1401
10	115	1401
Total	1275	14013

The 10-fold structure supports a standard cross-validation procedure. In each run, nine folds are used for training and one fold is held out for testing. By rotating the held-out fold, every POI is eventually used for both training and evaluation. This strategy maximizes the use of available data, reduces the risk of overfitting to a particular split, and provides a fair and comprehensive basis for comparing model performance across different subsets.

3.1.4 Data Preprocessing

In this section, we describe the preprocessing procedures applied to the filtered dataset to ensure that all inputs are transformed into a model-ready format. Given the multimodal nature of the task, preprocessing strategies are tailored to each input field, including titles, images, geo-context, and descriptions. The goal is to achieve consistent tokenization, normalization, and encodings while maintaining reproducibility across folds. All steps are implemented to avoid data leakage between training and evaluation sets.

Textual Preprocessing

Preprocessing of textual fields in this project primarily involves tokenization, which transforms raw text into sequences suitable for encoding and decoding within the multimodal framework. Accordingly, the `bert-base-uncased` tokenizer [55] is applied to POI titles and walker perspectives, as they are encoded by the BERT encoder, while the `GPT-2 tokenizer` [56] is applied to POI descriptions, which are generated by the GPT-2 decoder [57].

Both tokenizers are initialized from pretrained models available in the Hugging Face Transformers library [57]. To adapt them to the requirements of this project, the vocabularies are extended with a consistent set of special tokens:

```
"pad_token": <pad>
"unk_token": <unk>
"sep_token": <sep>
"bos_token": <s>
"eos_token": </s>
"additional_special_tokens": [<rep>]
```

These additions ensure uniform handling of padding, unknown tokens, and sequence boundaries across both encoder and decoder inputs.

Technically, the two tokenizers follow different principles: the BERT tokenizer applies the WordPiece algorithm [55], which splits uncommon words into smaller subwords, while the GPT-2 tokenizer applies Byte Pair Encoding (BPE) [56], which merges frequent

character sequences into larger subword units. This difference reflects their roles in the model: BERT is used to encode titles and perspectives for semantic representation, whereas GPT-2 is used to decode and generate fluent descriptions.

Because of these different principles, the preprocessing steps also differ. For BERT, normalization is a mandatory step, where all textual inputs such as titles and user perspectives are converted to lowercase to ensure consistency with the uncased pretrained model, while a prompt construction step can optionally be applied before tokenization of GPT-2. In this project, prompt construction is employed by concatenating each description with its title in the format "`<s> {title}. Description: {description} </s>`". The purpose of this design is to explicitly condition the decoder on the POI title, thereby guiding the model to generate descriptions that remain contextually aligned with the given POI. At the last step of the preprocessing, both tokenizers apply a length control to standardize input shapes: encoder inputs (titles and perspectives) are truncated or padded to **32 tokens**, while decoder outputs (descriptions) are truncated or padded to a maximum of **128 tokens**. As a result, both tokenizers produce two main outputs: (i) `input_ids`, which are integer indices representing tokens from the vocabulary, (ii) `attention_mask`, which distinguishes valid tokens (1) from padding tokens (0).

The following examples illustrate how each tokenizer processes textual inputs in practice.

Example: Title tokenized by BERT. The POI title “*St Helen’s Park*” is first normalized to lowercase and then segmented into subword units using the WordPiece algorithm. The resulting tokens are:

```
[CLS], st, hel, ##en, 's, park, [SEP]
```

These tokens are mapped to their vocabulary indices as shown below:

$$\text{input_ids} : \left[101, 2358, 6330, 1521, 1055, 2380, 102, \underbrace{0, 0, \dots, 0}_{25} \right]$$

$$\text{attention_mask} : \left[\underbrace{1, 1, \dots, 1}_7, \underbrace{0, 0, \dots, 0}_{25} \right]$$

Here, [101] and [102] represent the special [CLS] and [SEP] tokens, respectively. Padding tokens (0) are appended to ensure the fixed length of 32, while the attention mask distinguishes valid tokens (1) from padding (0).

Example: Description tokenized by GPT-2. On the decoder side, a conditional prompt is formed as:

```
<s> St Helen's Park. Description: St Helens Park
provide the perfect amount of shade while the footpaths
are far too small and the park furniture is in bad
shape. The park also provides a playground,
kindergarten and a nearby school. </s>
```

When processed by the GPT-2 tokenizer with a maximum length of 128 tokens, the output includes:

$$\text{input_ids} : \left[\begin{array}{l} 1273, 22695, 447, 247, 82, 3250, 13, 12489, 25, 520, \\ 5053, 641, 3250, 2148, 262, 2818, 2033, 286, 17979, 981, \\ 262, 2366, 6978, 82, 389, 1290, 1165, 1402, 290, 262, \\ 3952, 13091, 318, 287, 2089, 5485, 13, 262, 3952, 635, \\ 3769, 257, 24817, 11, 38717, 290, 257, 6716, 1524, 13, \\ \underbrace{50257, 50257, \dots, 50257}_{78} \end{array} \right]$$

$$\text{attention_mask} : \left[\underbrace{1, 1, \dots, 1}_{50}, \underbrace{0, 0, \dots, 0}_{78} \right]$$

Here, integers correspond to token indices from the GPT-2 vocabulary, while the padding value 50257 represents the added `<pad>` token. The attention mask marks valid tokens with 1s and padding tokens with 0s, ensuring that the decoder attends only to meaningful parts of the sequence.

This standardized preprocessing ensures comparability across textual fields and prepares them for efficient encoding within the multimodal framework.

Image Preprocessing

The preprocessing of POI images standardizes visual inputs into a consistent format tailored for the Vision Transformer (ViT) encoder. ViT models require all input images to share the same resolution and channel structure to facilitate uniform patch embedding and positional encoding, which are critical for attention-based processing and model performance [58, 59]. In this study, the pretrained `google/vit-base-patch16-224` model released through Hugging Face Transformers [57] is adopted, which expects images resized to 224×224 pixels. Accordingly, each POI image is converted into a three-channel RGB representation and resized to this resolution to preserve compatibility with pretrained weights and maintain the patching grid used in the ViT architecture [58].

Following resizing, images are normalized using the preprocessing scheme specific to the backbone (typically scaling pixel intensities to $[0, 1]$ and applying dataset-specific mean-std normalization). This step enhances training stability and convergence by ensuring a consistent value distribution across inputs, which is especially important for Transformers due to their sensitivity to input scaling [57, 60].

The processed image is then converted into a tensor in channel-first format $[C, H, W]$, where $C = 3$ corresponds to the RGB channels and $H = W = 224$ define the fixed spatial resolution. This format enables efficient patch extraction and embedding for the ViT encoder. During training or inference, if an image fails to load due to corruption or other issues, a zero-initialized placeholder tensor of the same shape is substituted to preserve input consistency. Finally, multiple preprocessed images are batched into a 4D tensor $[B, C, H, W]$, where B denotes the batch size. This 4D representation provides the standardized visual input for simultaneous processing by the model.

Geo-context Preprocessing

As detailed in Section 3.1.2, the geo-contextual enrichment process provides for each focal POI, a list of nearby POIs retrieved from OSM. Each near POI is characterized by its semantic type (e.g., bench, playground, historic site) and geographic coordinates, while the focal POI itself also has known coordinates. Since the modeling objective is to generate a description of the focal POI, the role of geo-context preprocessing is to establish meaningful spatial relationships between the focal POI and its surrounding environment, which in this project is concretely defined as the set of near POIs selected within a specified spatial extent.

Using raw latitude and longitude values for this purpose is not appropriate because geographic coordinates are expressed in angular degrees rather than linear distance units [61, 62], and their numeric differences do not correspond uniformly to real-world distances across the Earth’s surface. A difference of 0.001 degrees in longitude, for example, may represent hundreds of meters in Melbourne but only tens of meters near the poles [61]. More importantly, absolute coordinates provide no direct information about relative spatial structure. For description generation, what matters is not the exact global position of a POI, but how surrounding features are situated with respect to the focal POI, whether they are close or far, in which direction, and how densely they cluster [1].

Therefore, instead of feeding raw latitude and longitude into the model, the geo-context preprocessing transforms near POIs into relative representations that preserve local spatial relationships. In this study, two main strategies are employed to define the set of near POIs, which in turn shape how coordinates are transformed into contextual representations.

Formally, given a focal POI p_f with geographic coordinates (φ_f, λ_f) and a set of nearby POIs $\{p_i\}$ with coordinates (φ_i, λ_i) , we transform raw latitude/longitude into relative representations according to these two strategies:

Radius-based approach In this method, the focal POI is treated as the center of a circular neighborhood. All OSM features within a chosen radius are selected as near

POIs. The relative relationship is then established by transforming absolute coordinates into distance and directional offsets with respect to the focal POI.

Specifically, the angular differences are computed as:

$$\Delta\lambda = \lambda_i - \lambda_f, \quad \Delta\varphi = \varphi_i - \varphi_f.$$

These differences are then converted into distances in meters using a spherical Earth approximation with radius $R = 6,371,000$ m. For longitude differences, a cosine correction is applied to account for the variation in distance per degree across latitudes, resulting in:

$$\Delta x = \Delta\lambda \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\varphi_f\pi}{180}\right) \cdot \frac{\pi R}{180},$$

$$\Delta y = \Delta\varphi \cdot \frac{\pi R}{180}.$$

The resulting vector $(\Delta x, \Delta y)$ represents the planar offset of the nearby POI relative to the focal POI in meters. This encoding preserves both distance and directional information in consistent linear units, making it suitable for integration into the model.

Route-based approach The second method leverages the sequential structure of walking routes by adopting a Frenet coordinate system, which has been widely used in robotics and path planning to represent motion relative to a reference path [63]. In this system, the position of a point is decomposed into two components: the longitudinal displacement s along a reference curve, and the lateral offset d perpendicular to it. This representation has been shown to effectively capture sequential and directional relationships in structured environments such as urban streets, and here it is adapted to model walking routes.

Instead of applying a fixed-radius neighborhood, the environment is restricted to the corridor bounded by the previous and next POIs of the focal point. A centerline C is constructed from these points (either as a straight segment or a polyline), and all nearby POIs are described relative to this reference.

As a first step, all longitude/latitude coordinates are converted into local planar coordinates (x, y) in meters using a projection centered at the focal POI.

Let the previous POI be $p_{\text{prev}} = (x_{\text{prev}}, y_{\text{prev}})$, the next POI be $p_{\text{next}} = (x_{\text{next}}, y_{\text{next}})$, the focal POI be $p_f = (x_f, y_f)$, and a nearby POI be $p_i = (x_i, y_i)$.

Each nearby POI p_i is orthogonally projected onto the centerline C , yielding a projection point \hat{p}_i with an arc-length position s_i measured along C from p_{prev} . The focal POI itself has an arc-length position s_f . The longitudinal offset of p_i relative to the focal POI is then

$$\tilde{s}_i = s_i - s_f.$$

The lateral offset d_i is computed as the signed perpendicular distance from p_i to the segment $(p_{\text{prev}}, p_{\text{next}})$:

$$d_i = \frac{(x_{\text{next}} - x_{\text{prev}})(y_i - y_{\text{prev}}) - (y_{\text{next}} - y_{\text{prev}})(x_i - x_{\text{prev}})}{\sqrt{(x_{\text{next}} - x_{\text{prev}})^2 + (y_{\text{next}} - y_{\text{prev}})^2}}.$$

The sign of d_i indicates whether the nearby POI lies to the left or right side of the walking direction defined from p_{prev} to p_{next} .

Because corridors vary in size, both offsets are normalized for comparability across routes:

$$s'_i = \frac{\tilde{s}_i}{L}, \quad d'_i = \frac{d_i}{W},$$

where L is the total length of the corridor and W its predefined half-width. In this project, the half-width is fixed at $W = 100$ m for all corridors.

The normalized Frenet coordinates (s'_i, d'_i) thus provide a bounded, dimensionless representation that encodes whether a feature lies ahead or behind the focal POI (s'), and whether it is located to the left or right of the path (d'). This representation emphasizes sequential and directional relationships that are particularly relevant for modeling how walkers perceive their environment along a route.

3.2 Perspective Extraction

The previous sections have detailed how data is collected and preprocessed for integration into the multimodal framework. After data collection phase, three modalities, titles, images, and geo-context, have been successfully prepared for model integration. These modalities capture factual and objective aspects of POIs, such as names, appearances,

and surrounding environments. However, leisure walking is not solely shaped by factual attributes. Walkers often describe POIs through their personal perspectives, expressing emotions, preferences, or thematic interests (e.g., a quiet and relaxing atmosphere, a dog-friendly park, or a culturally enriched landmark).

To incorporate the human-centered dimension, this section introduces *perspective* as an additional input. It first defines the notion of perspective in the context of POI descriptions and explains its relation to user preferences. It then describes the sources of perspective signals available in the WalkingMaps dataset and outlines the methods used to extract them so that they can be incorporated with the other modalities in the multimodal framework.

3.2.1 Definition and Sources of Perspective Signals

In this research, *perspective* is defined as the subjective, human-centered dimension of a POI description that reflects how walkers perceive and evaluate a place. Unlike titles, images, or geo-context, which encode factual and objective attributes, perspectives capture walkers' personal interests, emotions, and thematic preferences. This factor also explains why descriptions of the same POI can be highly diverse. For example, as illustrated in Figure 3.6, multiple descriptions of *St Helen's Park* highlight contrasting aspects, ranging from practical facilities such as playgrounds, kindergartens, and well-maintained footpaths to more experiential impressions including interesting public art, accessibility for people with mobility needs, and the park's suitability for late-night walks. Even the same person may generate different descriptions of the same POI at different times, depending on what they find interesting on each occasion—for instance, focusing on *well-maintained footpaths* in one description and later on *the park's suitability for late-night walks*.

Perspectives are closely related to the concept of *user preferences*. In recommendation systems for POIs, preferences are understood as the underlying interests or needs of a user (e.g., seeking dog-friendly or culturally enriched routes). Perspectives, in turn, can be seen as the descriptive layer through which these preferences become observable, often expressed in narrative text or via selected features. Prior work on POI recommendation and contextual modeling has highlighted the central role of such user preferences, showing that information extracted from reviews, comments, or heterogeneous

contextual data substantially improves personalization and relevance of POI-related outputs [64, 65]. In the context of this thesis, perspectives provide the empirical foundation for addressing Research Question 2 posed in Section 1.4, which asks how a walker’s perspective can be effectively integrated into POI description generation for leisure walking. To put this concept into practice, it is necessary to identify observable signals through which perspectives are expressed in practice.

In the WalkingMaps dataset, such signals are expressed in two complementary forms:

Route Features

These features are predefined attributes that walkers can select when creating or sharing a walking route on the WalkingMaps web platform. In practice, the platform currently offers 15 such features, which can be found in the route creation interface (see Figure 3.7). Each feature describes a characteristic of the route or its POIs, such as the availability of seating, the presence of a playground, or cultural and historical interest.

FIGURE 3.7: Illustration of route-level features available on the WalkingMaps platform

Beyond route creation, the same set of attributes is also provided as search filters, allowing walkers to find routes that match their individual interests. By choosing from this set, walkers explicitly indicate what they consider important or valuable about the route.

This dual function makes route features particularly relevant as perspective signals: they capture subjective interests (e.g., child-friendly, dog-friendly, or culturally enriched walks) in an explicit and standardized form, directly reflecting what walkers value when selecting or describing a route. As such, route-level features provide a categorical and

structured representation of perspective that can be integrated into the multimodal framework.

While route features provide valuable categorical signals of walkers' general interests, they are assigned at the route level and not tailored to individual POIs. Using the entire set of features for description generation would therefore introduce noise, as not every selected feature is equally relevant to each POI along the route. In practice, only a subset—or even a single feature—may best align with the characteristics of a given POI. This limitation highlights the need for a complementary source of perspective signals that directly reference POIs themselves. Such signals are found in the free-text narratives contributed by walkers.

Narrative Descriptions of POIs.

Another important signal of perspective is the narrative description that walkers write and share for individual POIs. Unlike route features, which are selected once for an entire route and thus reflect only general preferences, these texts are directly attached to specific POIs. Narrative descriptions therefore provide fine-grained, POI-specific accounts that explicitly reveal walkers' emotions, preferences, and evaluations (e.g., *quiet and relaxing, colorful street art, safe for prams*). This makes them a main source of perspective signals.

Together, these two sources are complementary in extracting perspectives. Route features provide an explicit and standardized list of possible perspectives, while narrative descriptions offer rich and detailed accounts of walkers' experiences. By aligning the content of narratives with the predefined feature set, it becomes possible to infer which perspectives are most salient for each POI. The specific methods for extracting these perspectives are detailed in Section 3.2.2.

3.2.2 Extraction Method

The task of extracting thematic features from POI descriptions is closely related to topic modeling and text classification. In this project, three complementary approaches were investigated: a **rule-based method**, a **semantic similarity** approach using SentenceTransformer embeddings, and a **zero-shot classification** model. Each method

captures different aspects of thematic assignment, and their combination provides more comprehensive coverage.

Motivation for Ensemble Approach

Empirical analysis revealed that no single method was sufficient to achieve full coverage. A purely **rule-based approach** depends entirely on explicit keyword matches, leading to low recall when descriptions use synonyms or paraphrasing. Prior studies also emphasize that keyword-driven methods are brittle, with limited coverage in diverse, user-generated text [7, 66].

Embedding-based **semantic similarity** improves flexibility by capturing paraphrastic or semantically related expressions [52], while **zero-shot classification** enables inference without predefined labels, leveraging pretrained models for broader contextual understanding [67]. However, both similarity-based and zero-shot approaches rely on thresholding to assign labels, which in practice covers only a subset of the dataset with high confidence.

In practice, when applying these methods separately to the WalkingMaps dataset, with the current keyword set (nearly 200 keywords across 15 features), a total of around 25% of POI descriptions could not be assigned any feature because none of the defined keywords appeared in the text. Using a commonly adopted threshold of 0.5, the similarity method was able to confidently assign features to about 5,000 descriptions (33.5%), while the zero-shot classifier covered only approximately 800 descriptions (5.0%). The remaining descriptions fell below the threshold (66.5% and 95.0%, respectively), indicating that they could not be labeled with high confidence.

Since the objective of this study is to infer features for the *entire dataset*, an **ensemble approach** is adopted. By combining rule-based precision, embedding-based flexibility, and zero-shot contextual generalization, the pipeline balances the strengths of each method. This hybrid strategy follows prior evidence that ensemble methods generally achieve more robust performance in text classification tasks [68].

Simple Rule-based Approach

The rule-based approach is a straightforward method for assigning features to POI descriptions. Its principle relies on direct keyword matching: if a keyword associated with a feature appears in a description, that feature receives a score. Although simple, this approach provides a transparent and controllable baseline for feature extraction.

Workflow. The procedure of this method can be divided into three main steps:

1. **Data preparation.** All POI descriptions are normalized by converting to lowercase and removing punctuation, stop words, and special characters. This step ensures consistency and reduces noise before matching.
2. **Keyword building.** Each feature is represented by a curated list of keywords and phrases that signal its presence. The construction of this inventory followed an iterative process:
 - Start with three seed keywords per feature, chosen based on domain knowledge.
 - Apply these seed keywords to assign features to POI descriptions.
 - Collect all unmatched descriptions and extract the 30 most frequent non-stopword tokens from this subset.
 - Manually inspect these frequent tokens and, if semantically relevant, assign them to the appropriate feature.
 - Exclude generic high-frequency terms (e.g., *place*, *good*, *area*) that do not represent a distinctive theme.

This extract-inspect-assign cycle was repeated until approximately 75% of all POI descriptions contained at least one keyword. The final keyword inventory comprises nearly 200 entries across 15 features, ensuring broad coverage of the WalkingMaps dataset while maintaining semantic precision. The complete set of keywords is summarized in Appendix A.

3. **Scoring.** For each POI description, keyword occurrences are counted. Multiword phrases are prioritized for exact matching, while single words are lemmatized to increase robustness. The cumulative matches form the feature score for each description.

Semantic Similarity

The second method to extract thematic features builds on the curated keyword sets established in the rule-based approach (see Appendix A). Instead of relying solely on surface-level word matching, this method computes semantic similarity between POI descriptions and those predefined feature keywords using embedding-based representations.

The all-MiniLM-L6-v2 model from the Sentence-BERT family [52] was adopted, providing a lightweight yet effective solution for sentence-level semantic similarity. POI descriptions are preprocessed with spaCy: lemmatization is applied, stopwords are removed, and tokens shorter than three characters are discarded. This ensures consistent input text for embedding and reduces noise. All embedding vectors are then normalized to enable precise cosine similarity computation.

For each thematic feature, a set of representative keywords is used. Since these keywords are manually constructed in the rule-based step, they are already normalized and free from noise (e.g., no stopwords or spelling variations). Each keyword is therefore directly encoded into a 384-dimensional embedding vector using the Sentence-BERT model. The POI description, after standard text preprocessing, is encoded into a single embedding vector of the same dimension.

Then cosine similarity is computed between the POI embedding and each keyword embedding within a feature. The resulting similarity array is aggregated by taking the maximum value:

$$\text{score}(\text{feature}) = \max_{k \in K} (\text{cosine}(v_{\text{POI}}, v_k)),$$

where K is the set of keywords of the feature. This ensures that the strongest semantic match determines the feature’s score. The output is a continuous score for each feature, and no fixed threshold is applied at this stage. This design choice ensures that similarity values for all features are retained, allowing them to be combined later with scores from other extraction methods.

Zero-shot Classification

The third method for feature assignment is based on *zero-shot classification*, which leverages pretrained Natural Language Inference (NLI) models to predict the most plausible labels for a text without task-specific training. In NLI, the objective is to decide whether a *premise* entails, contradicts, or is neutral with respect to a *hypothesis*. This formulation has been widely applied to zero-shot text classification [67].

This study employs the Hugging Face `zero-shot-classification` pipeline [57] with the model `MoritzLaurer/deberta-v3-base-zeroshot-v2.0-c`, which is based on the DeBERTa-v3 architecture [69]. Each POI description is directly used as the input premise, without additional preprocessing.

The candidate labels correspond to the 15 thematic features defined for the walking routes. For each label f , the pipeline generates a hypothesis sentence using the default template “*This example is {f}.*” and computes the *entailment probability*, the likelihood that the POI description entails the hypothesis. The model outputs a normalized probability distribution over the 15 labels (softmax), with probabilities summing to one for each POI. I retain the complete set of scores for every feature label so that they can be directly combined with the outputs of the rule-based and semantic similarity methods in the ensemble step.

Ensemble Method

In this section, I describe how the outputs of the three approaches (rule-based, semantic similarity, and zero-shot classification) are combined into a single ensemble in order to assign the most relevant feature to each POI description. While each method provides complementary information, the ensemble integrates them into a unified scoring framework, from which one or several top-ranked features can be selected.

Since the raw scores of the three methods are not directly comparable (e.g., integer keyword counts versus cosine similarity versus NLI probabilities), all outputs are first normalized to form probability-like distributions over the set of 15 features. This ensures that each method contributes equally to the ensemble, independent of its original scoring range. For each POI and each feature f , the ensemble score is then computed as the

mean of the normalized scores across methods:

$$\hat{s}(f) = \frac{1}{3}(s_{\text{rule}}(f) + s_{\text{sim}}(f) + s_{\text{zshot}}(f)),$$

where s_{rule} , s_{sim} , and s_{zshot} denote the normalized scores from the rule-based, semantic similarity, and zero-shot methods, respectively. If a feature is absent from one method’s output, it contributes zero in that dimension.

The ensemble produces a complete score distribution over all features for each POI. Features are then ranked in descending order, allowing the selection of the top-1 feature (the single most relevant label) or top-k features (e.g., top-3). This averaging-based ensemble balances the complementary strengths of the three methods: rule-based counts emphasize explicit cues, semantic similarity captures lexical and contextual relatedness, and zero-shot NLI provides probabilistic judgments from a large pretrained model. By integrating them, the ensemble yields a more robust and reliable assignment of features than any individual method alone.

3.2.3 Illustrative Example

To illustrate how the three scoring methods and their ensemble operate, an example is presented using the POI “*The new path*” (walk_id: 3852) located on the Bondi to Coogee Coastal Walk, NSW. Its user-generated description is:

Finally, in 2021 a new path was created for the 6,000 or so people who walk this path each day (there was no path there before).

Rule-based: The keyword matching method identifies explicit overlaps between the POI description and the curated keyword inventory. In this example: the word “*path*” appears three times, matching the feature *Nature trail*. The description also contains the year “*2021*”, which triggers the temporal rule of *Historical interest*, adding one point.

Nature trail: 3,
Historical interest: 1

Semantic Similarity: Using Sentence-BERT embeddings, the description is compared with all feature keywords. The top-ranked features are:

Nature trail: 0.55,
Accessible walk: 0.48,
Public Transport: 0.39

Zero-shot Classification: The zero-shot method provides an alternative ranking based on a pretrained language model:

Accessible walk: 0.23,
Historical interest: 0.15,
Public Transport: 0.11

Ensemble: By combining the three methods with equal weights (for demonstration), the ensemble highlights the most salient features:

Nature trail: 0.30,
Historical interest: 0.15,
Accessible walk: 0.11

This example simply illustrates how the three scoring methods and their ensemble operate in practice. The complete scores for all 15 features of this POI description are listed in Appendix B.

3.3 Model Design

This section presents the architectural decisions underlying the proposed model. First of all, the encoder-decoder paradigm is adopted as the core architecture of the model. Basically, this architecture involves two components: an encoder that converts input sequences into dense representations, and a decoder that generates output sequences from these encodings [70]. There are two main reasons for this choice.

The first reason is the widespread adoption and proven effectiveness of the encoder-decoder architecture for text generation tasks. It is no doubt that the encoder-decoder architecture has become a dominant paradigm in a wide range of NLG tasks such as machine translation, text summarization, paraphrasing, dialogue generation, and data-to-text. Its prevalence stems from the flexibility of handling input and output sequences

of variable lengths, a critical feature in modeling complex natural language phenomena [70]. The architecture’s end-to-end learning framework enables direct mapping from input to output, which significantly reduces the cascading errors common in traditional modular pipelines [71]. Additionally, the encoder-decoder model serves as the foundation for many state-of-the-art models, most notably the Transformer architecture. Transformer-based models like T5 [72] and BART [73] retain the full encoder-decoder setup, allowing them to excel in a wide range of generative tasks, including summarization and conditional generation [74]. Encoder-decoder systems also support modular enhancements such as multiple encoders for integrating local/global context or external knowledge [75]. This capability also aligns well with the goals of this project, where one of the key challenges involves integrating heterogeneous information sources related to a given POI.

Both of the most recent studies on POI description generation have employed this architecture [1, 8]. As discussed in Chapter 2, Zhou et al. [8] proposed the MMDG, which integrates concatenated user reviews, POI categories, and spatial context through a multi-mode encoder. Reviews are encoded with a Transformer, categories are represented as one-hot embeddings, and spatial context is modeled via a context-aware CNN. These features are fused linearly and passed to a Transformer-based decoder for description generation. Building on this framework, Liu et al. [1] introduced GSGM, which advances the encoding of reviews and categories by using BERT, encodes spatial context with a Transformer-based spatial encoder, and replaces linear fusion with the novel Guide-Select mechanism. In this design, a *guider* aggregates global information across modalities, while a *selector* embedded in the GPT-2 decoder dynamically fuses relevant inputs based on the current decoding state. The overall architecture of GSGM is illustrated in Figure 3.8.

FIGURE 3.8: Overview of the Guide-Select Generative Model (GSGM) [1] architecture integrating multimodal inputs including reviews, categories, and spatial features.

Inspired by these works, the model proposed in this thesis adopts the fusion and decoder strategy of GSGM, while modifying the set of input modalities to better align with the leisure walking context. Specifically, the textual modality is reformulated to include both POI titles and walker perspectives, where the latter are extracted from existing POI descriptions to provide semantically rich signals tailored to leisure walking. In addition, a new visual modality is introduced, in which POI images are encoded using a Vision Transformer (ViT) [76] to capture perceptual and atmospheric cues that are difficult to convey in text alone. Finally, the spatial modality is redesigned to better reflect walking routes by incorporating preprocessed coordinates and type attributes of nearby POIs. The overall architecture of the proposed model is shown in Figure 3.9, where heterogeneous encoders produce modality-specific embeddings, which are fused through a guider mechanism before being decoded by GPT-2 with a selector module. These modifications extend GSGM by grounding description generation not only in textual and spatial signals, but also in visual features and walker-centered perspectives, making the model more suitable for leisure walking scenarios.

FIGURE 3.9: Overview of the proposed multimodal architecture for POI description generation.

The following sections present the detailed design of each component.

3.3.1 Encoders

Based on the collected dataset, three primary modalities are incorporated into the model design: textual, geo-contextual, and visual. Each modality captures complementary aspects of POIs in the leisure walking context, and in some cases, one modality may include multiple input types. To ensure that each source of information is effectively modeled, a dedicated encoder is assigned to every input type. The processing scheme is organized as follows:

Textual Modalities and Encoder

The Textual Encoder is responsible for modeling the linguistic information of POIs through two distinct textual inputs: the *Title* and the *Perspective*. These two inputs constitute the *Textual Modality* used in the model and capture different semantic aspects of POIs. While the *Title* represents the name or main identifier of a POI, whereas the *Perspective* conveys thematic and experiential content extracted from walker narratives.

Both textual inputs, the *Title* and the *Perspective*, are encoded independently using two BERT-based encoders that share the same architectural configuration, following and extending the design proposed by Liu [1]. Each encoder employs a pre-trained BERT backbone with selective fine-tuning of the last three Transformer layers (layers 9-11) to efficiently adapt to domain-specific linguistic patterns while preserving general language knowledge. The BERT outputs (dimension 768) are subsequently passed through a linear projection and layer normalization. Each BERT-based encoder contains approximately 46 million trainable parameters.

Spatial Modalities and Encoder

This modality represents the spatial environment around POIs and integrates two complementary sources of information. First, the *type attributes* of nearby POIs provide categorical textual cues that describe the functional roles of surrounding places. Second, the *spatial positions* of these nearby POIs are included, where raw latitude-longitude coordinates have been preprocessed into local spatial representations as described in Section 3.1.4. Together, these two components capture both the semantic and geometric structure of the environment, forming the basis of the *Geo-contextual Modality* used in the multimodal model.

The encoding of this modality is performed by a Transformer-based architecture, employed by Liu [1], to model spatial semantic relationships among nearby POIs. In this work, the same encoder structure is adopted and adapted to the leisure-walking domain, enabling integration with additional textual and visual modalities. The encoder jointly processes categorical information (types of nearby POIs) and their spatial positions to produce a unified embedding of the local environment. It consists of three main stages.

First, a **Type Embedding Layer** transforms the categorical attributes of nearby POIs into dense semantic vectors, while a **Location Embedding** module injects spatial information derived from two-dimensional coordinate encodings. These coordinate encodings are generated using a learnable interpolation mechanism that projects raw latitude longitude pairs into a continuous spatial feature space, preserving both local geometry and relative distance among POIs.

Second, these two sources of information are fused and augmented with **Positional Encoding**, enabling the model to capture the relative ordering and spatial layout of POIs.

Finally, the resulting representations are processed through a stack of six **Transformer Encoder Layers**, each employing multi-head self-attention to model relationships among nearby POIs such as functional similarity, spatial proximity, and clustering patterns within the environment.

The output of this encoder is a sequence of contextual embeddings that encapsulate how surrounding POIs are organized both semantically and spatially. These representations provide a structured description of the local geographic context, serving as a crucial input for multimodal fusion with textual and visual features. The overall architecture retains the parameter configuration of Liu et al.’s original design [1] (approximately 43 million trainable parameters), reflecting its ability to capture rich spatial semantic interactions while remaining computationally efficient for large-scale multimodal training.

Visual Modality and Encoder

The visual modality captures perceptual information from POI photographs, providing cues about their physical appearance, architectural features, and overall atmosphere. This modality is encoded using a ViT backbone [76], which extracts high-level visual features from POI images through a self-attention mechanism originally developed for image recognition tasks. Specifically, the encoder adopts the ViT-B/16 architecture implemented in the `torchvision.models`¹⁵ library, initialized with ImageNet pre-trained weights (`ViT_B_16_Weights.IMAGENET1K_V1`¹⁶).

To ensure dimensional consistency across modalities, the extracted visual feature vector (768-dimensional) is passed through a **Linear Projection Layer** that maps the ViT output into the shared multimodal embedding space, followed by a **Layer Normalization** step to stabilize feature distributions before fusion. The encoder thus transforms each input image tensor of shape [3, 224, 224] into a normalized embedding of shape [768], representing the overall visual characteristics of each POI.

¹⁵<https://pytorch.org/vision/stable/models.html>

¹⁶<https://docs.pytorch.org/vision/main/models>

All parameters of the ViT backbone are fine-tuned during training, allowing the model to adapt visual representations to the specific characteristics of POI imagery. The overall configuration contains approximately 86 million trainable parameters from the ViT-B/16 backbone, along with an additional 0.6 million parameters from the projection and normalization layers.

3.3.2 Cross-Modal Fusion

The multimodal fusion mechanism in this study follows the Guide-Select framework proposed by Liu et al. [1], which integrates heterogeneous information through a two-stage process consisting of a Guider and a Selector.

Guider

The *Guider* is a Transformer-based encoder. It is responsible for fusing information from multiple modalities (textual, spatial, and visual) into a unified representation while preserving the distinct characteristics of each modality. Rather than simply concatenating modality embeddings, the Guider performs structured multi-modal self-attention that allows interaction across modalities without losing their internal boundaries.

Each layer in the Guider contains two main components: a **Multi-modal Self-attention** mechanism with separate query-key-value projections for each modality, and a **Modality Specific Feed-forward Network**. These components ensure that the model captures interactions between modalities without one dominating the others.

Before fusion, each modality is normalized independently to reduce distributional differences. The normalized features are then concatenated and passed through several attention layers, progressively producing a unified representation that encodes both shared and modality-specific information. The model also tracks the boundary of each modality within the concatenated sequence, allowing precise alignment during attention and feed-forward computation.

Selector

The Selector is a lightweight adapter inserted into each layer of the decoder(GPT-2) after the Self-attention and Cross-attention layers but before the Feed-forward Network. Its main role is to refine the decoder’s hidden states by selectively fusing information from two complementary sources provided by the encoder:

- The **Global Fused Representation**, summarizing interactions across all modalities.
- The **Low-level Modality Representations** and their corresponding masks, which retain fine-grained details specific to each modality.

The adapter first normalizes the decoder hidden states and projects them into multi-head query vectors. It then performs a two-stage attention process that embodies the *selection* mechanism:

- **Modal-level Attention:** computes attention between the decoder’s hidden states and the guider representation of each modality to estimate which modality should be emphasized.
- **Token-level Attention:** within the selected modalities, computes fine-grained attention over token-level representations to capture specific content relevant to the current decoding step.

The two attentions are combined, allowing the Guider representation to act as a *gate* that determines the importance of each modality, while the Token-level attention refines the information within that modality. The fused result passes through a linear projection, dropout, and a residual connection to update the decoder hidden states.

This design allows the model to achieve balanced and interpretable fusion, where the guider establishes a unified global view and the selector dynamically retrieves fine-grained information relevant to the current linguistic context. As a result, Guide-Select enables effective integration of multimodal inputs while maintaining the distinct characteristics of each information source.

3.3.3 Decoder

The decoder is implemented as an extended version of **GPT-2**, which enables multi-modal fusion through both **cross-attention** and **adapter-based selection**.

The model builds on the pretrained `GPT2LMHeadModel` adding a cross attention part, allowing each decoder layer to attend to the fused encoder output. In particular, each Transformer block of GPT-2 is preserved the original pretrained weights and added two components:

- **Cross-attention Layer:** connects the decoder to the encoder’s guider representation, allowing each decoding step to be influenced by the global multimodal context.
- **Selector Adapter Module:** a lightweight adapter described in Section 3.3.2, responsible for injecting fine-grained multimodal information from both the Guider output and Low-level Modality Representations.

During the forward pass, each block performs the following sequence of operations:

- Self-attention and residual connection to model dependencies within the generated sequence.
- Cross-attention to the encoder output followed by another residual connection.
- The *Selector Adapter* integrates the guider output and low-level representations based on their corresponding masks.
- A feed-forward layer with residual connection completes the computation.

During generation, all adapter inputs, including the guider output and the multimodal representations, are expanded consistently across beam hypotheses so that every decoding path has access to the same multimodal context.

3.4 Evaluation Metrics

The evaluation of generated POI descriptions relies on three quantitative metrics that together capture lexical accuracy, semantic fidelity, and textual diversity. While BLEU

and CIDEr assess how closely the generated text matches the reference descriptions, BERTScore provides a deeper measure of semantic alignment. An additional metric, DISTINCT, is used exclusively in the inference length analysis to evaluate the diversity and repetitiveness of generated outputs.

3.4.1 BLEU

BLEU (Bilingual Evaluation Understudy) is a precision-based metric originally developed for machine translation evaluation [44]. It remains one of the most widely adopted metrics for text generation tasks due to its simplicity, interpretability, and reproducibility. Both Zhou et al. [8] and Liu et al. [1] employed BLEU in their POI description generation models, and its inclusion here enables direct comparability with these studies.

Computation: BLEU measures the degree of n -gram overlap between a generated text (candidate) and one or more reference texts. It combines a modified n -gram precision with a brevity penalty to discourage excessively short outputs. The overall BLEU score is computed as:

$$BLEU = BP \times \exp \left(\sum_{n=1}^N w_n \log p_n \right)$$

where p_n denotes the modified n -gram precision for n -grams of size n , w_n is the weight for each n (typically uniform, i.e., $w_n = \frac{1}{N}$), and BP is the brevity penalty defined as $BP = 1$ if $c > r$, else $BP = \exp(1 - \frac{r}{c})$, with c and r being the lengths of the candidate and reference, respectively. The BLEU score ranges from 0 to 1 (often reported as a percentage), with higher values indicating greater lexical similarity to the reference. According to the Hugging Face evaluation guide¹⁷, BLEU scores ranged from 0.0527 to 0.2571 across five translation systems on a 500-sentence corpus.

Properties: BLEU is computationally efficient, language-independent, and correlates moderately well with human judgments in structured generation tasks [77]. It effectively captures local fluency and grammatical correctness when the reference phrasing is relatively fixed. However, it does not account for semantic equivalence or paraphrastic variation, and it tends to undervalue creative but valid expressions [78]. BLEU is

¹⁷<https://huggingface.co/spaces/evaluate-metric/bleu>

also sensitive to sentence length—shorter outputs often yield higher precision but lower recall [77].

Implementation: In this study, BLEU is computed at the corpus level to obtain a single, aggregate score representing the overall agreement between generated and reference descriptions. This approach follows the standard practice in text generation evaluation and ensures consistency with previous POI description models [1, 8]. Corpus-level BLEU calculates n -gram precision across all sentences in the test set rather than averaging sentence-level scores, which makes it less sensitive to fluctuations in very short descriptions—a frequent characteristic of POI datasets. The metric is implemented using the Hugging Face `evaluate` library, which reproduces the official BLEU algorithm and has been widely adopted in recent NLP research.

3.4.2 CIDEr

CIDEr (Consensus-based Image Description Evaluation) is a metric specifically designed for evaluating image captioning and other descriptive text generation tasks [79]. Since the proposed model incorporates visual inputs, this metric is selected as it aligns well with the multimodal and descriptive nature of the task.

Computation: CIDEr computes a weighted cosine similarity between TF-IDF representations of n -grams extracted from the candidate and reference descriptions. Each n -gram is assigned a term frequency (TF) and an inverse document frequency (IDF) to emphasize informative and distinctive content words. The CIDEr score for a single candidate sentence is defined as:

$$\text{CIDEr}(c_i, S_i) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{n=1}^N w_n \frac{g^n(c_i) \cdot g^n(s_{ij})}{\|g^n(c_i)\| \|g^n(s_{ij})\|}$$

where c_i denotes the candidate description, $S_i = \{s_{i1}, \dots, s_{im}\}$ is the set of m reference descriptions, $g^n(\cdot)$ is the TF-IDF vector for n -grams of order n , and w_n is the weight (typically uniform). The final CIDEr score is the average of all sentence-level scores across the corpus. Scores range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating stronger agreement between the generated and reference descriptions.

Properties: CIDEr has been shown to correlate strongly with human judgments in descriptive generation tasks [79]. It performs particularly well when there are multiple

valid references, as it quantifies the degree of semantic consensus rather than strict lexical overlap. However, its reliance on reference variability means that it may be less stable in single-reference datasets [80]. Additionally, because TF-IDF weighting depends on the entire corpus, CIDEr is slightly more computationally intensive than BLEU, though still efficient for evaluation purposes [79].

Implementation: In this project, CIDEr is computed using the implementation from the `pycocoevalcap` package¹⁸, following the standard COCO evaluation protocol. This protocol, introduced as part of the Microsoft COCO Captioning Challenge [81, 82], provides a unified framework for evaluating image description systems using multiple reference captions per image.

3.4.3 BERTScore

BERTScore is a semantic evaluation metric that measures the contextual similarity between generated and reference texts using embeddings from a pretrained BERT model [83]. This metric is included in this study due to its strong correlation with human judgments in recent NLG research [84]. The inclusion of BERTScore provides a complementary perspective on model performance beyond the lexical comparisons of BLEU and CIDEr.

Computation: BERTScore represents each token in both the candidate and reference sentences as contextual embeddings derived from a pretrained transformer (typically BERT). The similarity between each candidate token and its most similar reference token is computed using cosine similarity, from which precision (P), recall (R), and F_1 are derived as:

$$P = \frac{1}{|X|} \sum_{x \in X} \max_{y \in Y} \cos(e_x, e_y), \quad R = \frac{1}{|Y|} \sum_{y \in Y} \max_{x \in X} \cos(e_y, e_x), \quad F_1 = \frac{2PR}{P + R}$$

where X and Y denote the token sets of the candidate and reference texts, and e_x, e_y are their embedding vectors. In this study, the F_1 variant is used, as it balances faithfulness (precision) and completeness (recall) in conveying meaning.

Properties: BERTScore is particularly effective when multiple valid ways of expressing the same meaning exist. Its main advantage is the ability to evaluate semantic fidelity

¹⁸<https://github.com/salaniz/pycocoevalcap>

independently of surface wording. However, it can be sensitive to the choice of the pretrained model and may slightly favor longer outputs due to token-level averaging [85].

Implementation: For implementation, BERTScore is computed using the official implementation provided by Hugging Face¹⁹. The pretrained model used is `bert-base-uncased`, which is motivated by both practicality and methodological consistency. This model represents the original English configuration of Pre-training BERT [55] and serves as the default pretrained checkpoint distributed through the Hugging Face library. It is trained on large-scale English corpora (BookCorpus and English Wikipedia) and has been widely used as the standard backbone for text similarity and evaluation tasks in English NLG research [86]. Compared to larger variants, the base model provides a balanced trade-off between computational efficiency and robust semantic representation, making it particularly suitable for large-scale evaluation such as cross-validation across multiple folds.

3.4.4 Distinct-n.

Distinct [87] is a lexical diversity metric designed to evaluate how varied the generated text is in terms of vocabulary usage. It provides a simple and effective way to quantify the amount of repetition in model outputs, which is particularly useful for analyzing generated text length and fluency.

Computation: The metric measures the proportion of unique n -grams in the generated text, where higher scores indicate more diverse and less repetitive language. Two variants are commonly reported: **Distinct-1** for unigram diversity and **Distinct-2** for bigram diversity. Both are computed as:

$$\text{Distinct-n} = \frac{\text{Number of unique } n\text{-grams}}{\text{Total number of } n\text{-grams}}.$$

Properties: Distinct is computationally simple and provides an interpretable measure of lexical diversity. A higher value indicates that the model produces richer, less repetitive language, which can be desirable for generative tasks. However, the metric is highly sensitive to sequence length—longer outputs tend to contain more repeated tokens, which lowers the score even if the text remains fluent and coherent. Moreover, Distinct does

¹⁹<https://huggingface.co/spaces/evaluate-metric/bertscore>

not account for semantic quality or contextual appropriateness, making it less suitable as a standalone evaluation metric for NLG quality. Instead, it complements other metrics by highlighting the trade-off between text length and diversity [87, 88].

Implementation: For this project, Distinct-1 and Distinct-2 are computed at the corpus level across all generated POI descriptions. The metric counts unique unigrams and bigrams using a simple whitespace-based word tokenization and computes their ratios to the total number of n -grams. These values are reported only in the experiments concerning inference length, as lexical diversity is particularly sensitive to output length.

Chapter 4

Experiments and Results

This Chapter describes the experiments used to evaluate the proposed multimodal model for POI description generation and presents their results. The experiments are designed to answer the research questions presented in Section 1.4 by systematically assessing the contribution of different input modalities and the integration of walker perspectives.

4.1 Objectives

The experiments, comprising both preliminary parameter setup and main evaluation tasks, are designed to address the research questions, while also adapting the experimental setup to the characteristics of the WalkingMaps dataset. Specifically:

- **Inference length analysis.** NLG models generally learn when to end a sequence, but the length of generated text can also be influenced by setting minimum and maximum length parameters at inference time. These parameters are highly dependent on dataset characteristics. For instance, route descriptions on many platforms are limited to a few thousand characters (up to 2000 characters on WalkingMaps), while POI descriptions are typically much shorter, usually below 200 characters on WalkingMaps. Choosing different minimum or maximum lengths can therefore directly affect the performance of models. Accordingly, one objective of the experiments is to determine suitable min-max length settings for our dataset, ensuring that generated descriptions exhibit natural verbosity and align with reference texts. This step does not directly address the research questions or

test the hypotheses, but ensure that subsequent experiments are conducted under optimal generation parameters.

- **Geo-context representation analysis.** Although this is not explicitly stated as a research question, it is necessary because the geo-context encoding method used by Liu et al. [1] for GSGM does not directly align with the walking scenario. As discussed in Section 3.1.2, three alternative strategies for retrieving nearby POIs were developed (radius-based with urban-aware scaling, segment corridor, and polyline corridor). This experiment examines whether different geo-context representations lead to noticeable differences in the GSGM baseline, and thus establishes a reliable basis for subsequent experiments.
- **Main modality experiments.** Lastly, and most importantly, the experiments examine the role of image and walker perspective. The goal of this step is to directly address the research questions by evaluating whether visual information enhances the descriptiveness of generated POI content, and whether perspective signals enable the descriptions to better reflect walkers' experiences.

4.2 Setup

4.2.1 Environment

All experiments are implemented in Python 3.8 using PyTorch as the main deep learning framework. Pre-trained models and tokenizers (BERT, GPT-2, and ViT) are obtained via the HuggingFace Transformers library¹, with local paths configured for reproducibility. Supporting libraries include `torchvision`² for image preprocessing, and other standard Python packages.

The experiments are conducted on a virtual Linux server provisioned through the Research Computing Platform (RCP)³ at the University of Melbourne. The server is equipped with an NVIDIA L40S-24Q GPU with 24 GB VRAM. The system uses NVIDIA driver version 535.183.06 and CUDA 12.2 with cuDNN support.

¹<https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/en/index>

²<https://docs.pytorch.org/vision/stable/index.html>

³<https://rcp.research.unimelb.edu.au/>

The experiments are conducted on the custom dataset collected, constructed, and cleaned from WalkingMaps and OSM (Section 3.1). This dataset integrates textual descriptions, geo-coordinates, and user-uploaded images for around 14,000 POIs across 2,000 walking routes. The dataset is then partitioned into 10 fixed folds. The detailed splitting procedure and statistics of each fold are provided in Section 3.1.3.

4.2.2 Training Configuration

All models are trained using the custom training pipeline implemented for this thesis. Training follows the configuration strategy of GSGM [1], with consistent settings applied across all experiments to ensure comparability between modality variants.

Optimizer and learning rate. Parameters are optimized using the AdamW optimizer with a fixed learning rate of 1×10^{-4} . This configuration is widely adopted in the Hugging Face `transformers` library for fine-tuning pretrained models such as BERT and GPT. Using a relatively small fixed learning rate helps prevent catastrophic forgetting by preserving the pretrained weights while allowing gradual adaptation to the downstream task [57].

Batch size. The batch size varies depending on the experimental condition and available GPU memory. In the multimodal settings that include spatial corridors and images, batch sizes of 20 are used, while larger batch sizes (up to 32) are employed in textual only modality configuration.

Epochs and early stopping. Training is run for a maximum of 50 epochs with an early stopping patience of 5 based on validation loss. This setting is conservative compared to Liu et al. [1], who trained their GSGM model for up to 400 epochs with a patience of 10. The lower bound adopted here reflects practical considerations of computational resources and time constraints. While the proposed model fine-tunes not only the encoders but also the fusion and decoder layers, the use of early stopping ensures that effective convergence can still be achieved within this limit. Thus, the 50-epoch cap strikes a balance between ensuring sufficient training for multimodal integration and maintaining feasible runtime for extensive cross-validation experiments.

Cross-validation. To ensure robustness, all experiments are conducted under a 10-fold cross-validation scheme, with models trained separately for each fold. The dataset

splits are fixed and consistent across modalities (see Section 3.1.3). For each fold, the evaluation metrics that are described in Section 3.4 are computed independently on the validation subset. The final performance of a model configuration is reported as the mean and standard deviation of these metrics across all folds, providing a comprehensive measure of stability and generalization.

Finally, statistical tests are conducted to determine whether the performance differences between models are statistically significant. Specifically, the Wilcoxon test is applied to compare modality variants and geo-context representations. This procedure ensures that the observed performance differences are not due to random variations in data partitioning but instead reflect consistent model behavior across folds.

Given the small number of pairwise comparisons (10 folds) and the exploratory nature of the analysis, no multiple-comparison correction is applied. The tests are intended to indicate general performance trends across different modality combinations and geo-context representations, rather than to establish strict statistical significance.

In summary, the training configuration prioritizes comparability across experiments rather than hyperparameter optimization. This setup ensures that differences in performance can be attributed to the role of input modalities and the integration of walker perspectives, rather than variations in training conditions.

4.3 Experimental Details and Results

In accordance with the three main objectives identified in Section 4.1, three corresponding experiment blocks are designed. All experiments share the same configuration settings described in Section 4.2.2 to ensure comparability across conditions.

4.3.1 Experiment 1: Inference Length Calibration

Objective

To determine suitable values of the decoder’s `min_length` and `max_length` parameters that produce POI descriptions of natural verbosity, consistent with the WalkingMaps dataset.

Setup

The model architecture follows the encoder-fusion-decoder design described in Section 3.3. In this experiment, only the textual modality is used, with **Title** as the sole input. All encoder, decoder, and fusion components remain identical to the main multimodal configuration; the only varying factors are the `min_length` and `max_length` parameters of the GPT-2 decoder during inference. These parameters define the allowable range of generated text lengths (in tokens) and control when the model is permitted to stop generation.

TABLE 4.1: Configuration for Experiment 1.
All components follow the design in Section 3.3, The decoder’s inference parameters (`min_length`, `max_length`) are varied.

Component	Configuration
Input modality	Title (text).
Encoder	Following Section 3.3.1.
Fusion module	Following Section 3.3.2.
Decoder (GPT-2)	Training: Following Section 3.3.3. Inference: Varying <code>min_length</code> and <code>max_length</code> . Detail in Table 4.2
Evaluation Metrics	Distinct-1, Distinct-2, BERTScore

The parameter sets are selected based on the empirical distribution of ground-truth description lengths in the WalkingMaps dataset.(see Figure 4.1). In particular, Most POI descriptions contain between 20 and 50 tokens, with a median of 34 and a maximum of 131 tokens. The quartile values (25th = 24, 75th = 45) and the observed minimum (9) and maximum (131) provide a practical basis for defining reasonable decoding constraints.

FIGURE 4.1: Token length distribution for POI descriptions in the WalkingMaps dataset

To capture different verbosity levels, two representative lower bounds (`min_length = 10` and `25`) are chosen near the minimum and first quartile, and two upper bounds (`max_length = 45` and `135`) are selected near the third quartile and slightly above the observed maximum to allow for natural completion during generation. These values are combined in a cross-pairing scheme to explore both concise and verbose decoding regimes, as summarized in Table 4.2.

TABLE 4.2: Min-max decoding length configurations derived from the empirical token-length distribution.
(All lengths are measured in decoder tokens.)

Configuration ID	Min length	Max length
L10_45	10	45
L10_135	10	135
L25_45	25	45
L25_135	25	135

The evaluation of this experiment focuses primarily on the **Distinct-1** and **Distinct-2** metrics, which measure the lexical *richness* and *repetitiveness* of the generated descriptions. In addition, **BERTScore-F1** is included to assess the *semantic similarity* between the generated text and the ground-truth descriptions. While Distinct metrics capture the diversity of language use, BERTScore ensures that the generated text remains semantically faithful to human-written references. Together, these metrics support the

identification of a decoder length configuration (`min_length`, `max_length`) that achieves a balance between linguistic diversity and semantic accuracy, allowing the model to generate descriptions that are both expressive and meaningfully aligned with the original POI content.

Results

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.2 are presented to reports the experimental results for different decoder length configurations including the averaged and distribution of the three scores across ten cross-validation folds for each combination of `min_length` and `max_length`. Among the four configurations, L10_45 (`min_length`=10, `max_length`=45) attains the highest scores in both Distinct metrics while maintaining strong BERTScore performance. By contrast, configurations with larger `max_length` values (135) consistently yield lower results across all metrics, indicating that overly long decoding ranges reduce both linguistic diversity and semantic precision.

TABLE 4.3: Average performance of different decoding length configurations over 10 folds.

Configuration	Min	Max	BERTScore	Distinct-1	Distinct-2
L10_45	10	45	0.571	0.197	0.556
L10_135	10	135	0.568	0.188	0.543
L25_45	25	45	0.570	0.196	0.554
L25_135	25	135	0.569	0.187	0.542

FIGURE 4.2: Boxplots of Distinct and BERTScore metrics across decoder length configurations. Configurations with shorter maximum lengths (`max_length=45`) consistently yield higher and more stable scores.

To validate whether the observed differences among decoding length configurations are statistically significant, a series of non-parametric tests are performed over the ten cross-validation folds. The result of Friedman test is detailed in Table 4.4.

TABLE 4.4: Results of the Friedman test for Experiment 1 (10 folds, $N = 4$ configurations). All metrics show significant overall differences among decoding length settings.

Metric	Chi-square (χ^2)	p-value
Distinct-1	30.000	< 0.001
Distinct-2	30.000	< 0.001
BERTScore	30.000	< 0.001

Under the null hypothesis (H_0) that: "There is no significant difference in model performance across the four decoding length configurations", the Friedman test yields a chi-square statistic of $\chi^2 = 30.000$ with a corresponding $p < 0.001$. This result leads

to the rejection of H_0 , indicating that decoding length has a statistically significant effect on all evaluated metrics. In other words, variations in `min_length` and `max_length` meaningfully influence both the lexical diversity and semantic quality of the generated POI descriptions.

Following the overall significance observed in the Friedman test, pairwise Wilcoxon signed-rank tests are conducted for all configuration pairs to identify specific differences. The null hypothesis (H_0) for each pairwise comparison states that: "There is no difference in the median performance between the two configurations". The detailed results are presented in Table 4.5.

TABLE 4.5: Summary of Friedman and Pairwise Wilcoxon test results for Experiment 1.
(✓= significant difference, ✗= not significant)

Metric	Config 1	Config 2	Statistic	p-value	Signif.
Distinct-1	L10_45	L25_45	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L10_45	L10_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L10_45	L25_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L25_45	L10_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L25_45	L25_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L10_135	L25_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
Distinct-2	L10_45	L25_45	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L10_45	L10_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L10_45	L25_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L25_45	L10_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L25_45	L25_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L10_135	L25_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
BERTScore-F1	L10_45	L25_45	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L10_45	L10_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L10_45	L25_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L25_45	L10_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L25_45	L25_135	0.0	0.00195	✓
	L10_135	L25_135	0.0	0.00195	✓

All pairwise tests return $p < 0.005$, leading to the rejection of H_0 in every case (Table 4.5). Across all metrics, the rank ordering of configurations remains consistent: L10_45 achieves the highest scores, followed by L25_45, while both long-length settings (L10_135 and L25_135) perform notably worse. This ordering holds for all three evaluation metrics (Distinct-1, Distinct-2, and BERTScore-F1), indicating that shorter decoding constraints (`max_length=45`) yield outputs that are both lexically richer and semantically more faithful to the reference descriptions.

The superiority of shorter decoding constraints in this experiment can be interpreted from three complementary factors.

- **Model behavior.** Transformer-based decoders such as GPT-2 generate text autoregressively, where each token is conditioned on all previously generated tokens. When the allowable length range is too wide, the model tends to over-generate by repeating phrases or appending generic, low-information segments [89], which degrades both lexical diversity (Distinct-1/2) and semantic alignment with the reference text (lower BERTScore).
- **Metric sensitivity.** The Distinct metrics themselves are inherently sensitive to sequence length [87]. Because they compute the ratio of unique n -grams to the total number of n -grams, longer outputs naturally exhibit more repetition, leading to lower Distinct scores even when the content remains fluent.
- **Dataset characteristics.** The observed pattern also reflects the empirical nature of the WalkingMaps dataset, where human-written POI descriptions are naturally concise, approximately 75% of all descriptions contain fewer than 45 tokens.

Among these factors, the dataset characteristic is the most influential. Selecting a shorter decoding configuration is therefore well justified, as shorter decoding limits not only prevent over-generation but also conform to the structural norms of the training data, producing outputs that are both semantically precise and linguistically natural.

4.3.2 Experiment 2: Geo-context Representation Analysis

Objective

To examine how different definitions of **geo-context** that is how nearby POIs are spatially retrieved and represented, affect the performance of POI description generation, and to identify which representation provides the most informative and balanced spatial context. Although geo-context representation is not a primary research question, this analysis is essential because the spatial context definition adopted in previous work (e.g., GSGM [1]) assumes a simple fixed-radius neighborhood, which may not align with the linear and route-oriented nature of leisure walking.

Setup

This experiment uses the textual-spatial configuration (**Title + Geo-context**) without visual modality. All components follow the same encoder-fusion-decoder design introduced in Section 3.3.

TABLE 4.6: Configuration for Experiment 2.
All components follow the design in Section 3.3, with variation in the geo-context representation.

Component	Configuration
Input modality	Title (text) + Geo-context (spatial).
Encoder	Following Section 3.3.1
Fusion module	Guide-Select fusion mechanism (Section 3.3.2).
Decoder (GPT-2)	Following Section 3.3.3 (with <code>min_length=10</code> , <code>max_length=45</code>)
Evaluation Metrics	BLEU, CIDEr, BERTScore.

The only varying factor is the method used to retrieve nearby POIs as spatial input. Four geo-context construction strategies are evaluated in this experiment. The first variant, *Fixed Radius (FIX-RAD)*, directly reproduces the static 1000,m neighborhood used in GSGM [1], serving as the baseline for comparison. The second variant, *Density-Aware Radius (DEN-RAD)*, adapts the retrieval radius according to regional population

density, as detailed in Section 3.1.2, to balance the number of contextual POIs retrieved in urban versus rural settings. The third and fourth variants, *Segment Corridor (SEG-COR)* and *Polyline Corridor (POLY-COR)*, are both route-based approaches introduced in Section 3.1.2.

TABLE 4.7: Geo-context representation variants evaluated in Experiment 2.

ID	Name	Description / Reference Section
FIX-RAD	Fixed Radius (Baseline)	Directly reproduces the fixed 1000 m neighborhood in GSGM [1].
DEN-RAD	Radius-Density Aware Scaling	Dynamically scales the contextual radius based on ABS population density levels (Section 3.1.2).
SEG-COR	Segment Corridor	Retrieves nearby POIs within route segments buffered by adaptive width (Section 3.1.2).
POLY-COR	Polyline Corridor	Defines contextual POIs along the full polyline route corridor (Section 3.1.2).

The performance of each spatial variant is evaluated using three complementary metrics—**BLEU**, **CIDEr**, and **BERTScore**, which together assess the lexical accuracy, content relevance, and semantic similarity of the generated POI descriptions with respect to human-written references.

Results

The average results across ten folds are summarized in Table 4.8, and the corresponding score distributions are illustrated in Figure 4.3. All proposed geo-context configurations outperform the fixed-radius baseline (**FIX-RAD**), with the route-based approaches (**SEG-COR** and **POLY-COR**) achieving the highest scores overall.

TABLE 4.8: Average Metrics by Geo-context Configuration.

Configuration	Name	BLEU	CIDEr	BERTScore
FIX-RAD	Fixed Radius	0.1566	0.6774	0.5607
DEN-RAD	Density Aware	0.1568	0.7036	0.5638
SEG-COR	Segment Corridor	0.1546	0.7389	0.5693
POLY-COR	Segment Corridor	0.1566	0.7400	0.5708

FIGURE 4.3: Boxplots of BLEU, CIDEr, BERTScore metrics across geo-context configurations.

To verify whether these differences are statistically significant, the Friedman and pairwise Wilcoxon signed-rank tests are conducted. The results are summarized in Table 4.9.

TABLE 4.9: Summary of Friedman and Pairwise Wilcoxon test results for Experiment 2.
(✓= significant difference, ✗= not significant)

Metric	Comparison	Statistic	p-value	Signif.
Friedman Test				
BLEU	–	$\chi^2 = 5.640$	0.130	✗
CIDEr	–	$\chi^2 = 17.760$	0.0005	✓
BERTScore	–	$\chi^2 = 27.000$	< 0.001	✓
Pairwise Wilcoxon Tests				
CIDEr	FIX-RAD vs DEN-RAD	7.0	0.037	✓
	FIX-RAD vs SEG-COR	0.0	0.002	✓
	FIX-RAD vs POLY-COR	1.0	0.004	✓
	DEN-RAD vs SEG-COR	3.0	0.010	✓
	DEN-RAD vs POLY-COR	1.0	0.004	✓
	SEG-COR vs POLY-COR	24.0	0.770	✗
BERTScore	FIX-RAD vs DEN-RAD	2.0	0.006	✓
	FIX-RAD vs SEG-COR	0.0	0.002	✓
	FIX-RAD vs POLY-COR	0.0	0.002	✓
	DEN-RAD vs SEG-COR	0.0	0.002	✓
	DEN-RAD vs POLY-COR	0.0	0.002	✓
	SEG-COR vs POLY-COR	6.0	0.027	✓

Looking into the results in more detail, the BLEU values remain relatively stable across all configurations (around 0.156), whereas both CIDEr and BERTScore consistently improve when moving from the fixed-radius baseline to the density-aware and then to the route-based approaches.

Among the route-based strategies, however no substantial differences are observed between the two corridor-based configurations. For both BLEU and CIDEr, the differences between SEG-COR and POLY-COR are not statistically significant, indicating that the two methods perform similarly in terms of lexical overlap and content relevance. Although a statistically significant difference is detected for BERTScore, the margin is minimal, with the average score of POLY-COR (0.5708) only 0.002 higher than that of

SEG-COR (0.5693). This suggests that, while the polyline corridor provides a slightly stronger semantic alignment with reference descriptions, both corridor-based representations achieve comparable overall performance.

To understand why their performance remains so similar, it is useful to examine the underlying geometric relationship between the two corridor definitions. The degree of spatial overlap between these representations can be analyzed by comparing their geometric lengths. As mentioned in Section 3.1.2, both SEG-COR and POLY-COR are geometric interpolations derived from the sequence of POIs described by walkers rather than the actual walking path. In this setup, SEG-COR represents the straight line connecting the previous and next POIs around the current one, forming a locally bounded corridor centered on the target point, whereas POLY-COR connects the same three points (*prev-POI-next*) into a short polyline that slightly extends along the directional path implied by the walker’s narrative. If the polyline length is considerably greater than the direct segment distance, it suggests that the local POI arrangement forms a curved or articulated pattern; otherwise, similar lengths indicate that the POIs are nearly aligned, and the two corridor areas largely overlap or the path is straight.

To further validate this geometric interpretation, the length ratios between the polyline and segment corridors are analyzed across all POIs. As shown in Table 4.10, approximately 90% of the ratios are below 2, and about 75% fall below 1.2. In addition, around 20% instances have equal lengths for both segment and polyline definitions. This confirms that, in most cases, the two corridor types capture nearly identical spatial extents. The minor deviations that exist mainly occur along curved or irregular routes, where the polyline extends slightly farther along the walking direction.

TABLE 4.10: Length ratio statistics and distribution
 $(r = \text{Length}_{\text{polyline}} / \text{Length}_{\text{segment}})$.

(a) Descriptive Statistics Ratio		(b) Distribution by Ratio Range		
Statistic	Value	Ratio Range	Count	(%)
Minimum	1.000	< 1	2,697	17.64
Maximum	1014	1-2	11,289	73.85
Mean	1.579	2-3	676	4.42
First Quartile (25%)	1.000	3-4	215	1.41
Median (50%)	1.025	4-5	120	0.78
Third Quartile (75%)	1.207	> 5	290	1.90

TABLE 4.11: Descriptive statistics of absolute length differences
 $(\Delta = \text{Length}_{\text{polyline}} - \text{Length}_{\text{segment}})$.

Statistic	Value (m)
Minimum	0
Maximum	7,140
Mean	73
Standard Deviation	243
First Quartile (25%)	0.08
Median (50%)	7
Third Quartile (75%)	50

To investigate whether such geometric deviations have any impact on model performance, an additional analysis is conducted by separating the POIs according to their absolute length difference ($\Delta = \text{Length}_{\text{polyline}} - \text{Length}_{\text{segment}}$). Specifically, POIs with $\Delta > 50$ m, corresponding to the top 25% of all cases, as the third quartile reported in Table 4.11, are selected. This threshold effectively isolates the subset of POIs where the two corridor definitions diverge more noticeably.

TABLE 4.12: Comparison of model performance for POIs with large geometric deviations ($\Delta > 50$ m).

Metric	Segment	Polyline	p -value (Wilcoxon)
BLEU	0.143	0.144	0.057
CIDEr	0.710	0.729	0.119
BERTScore	0.569	0.570	0.031

A total of 3,833 POIs fall into this subset. Table 4.12 summarizes the average performance metrics and the results of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test comparing the Segment- and Polyline-based configurations.

- **BLEU & CIDEr:** While the Polyline corridor yields slightly higher average BLEU and CIDEr scores, these differences are not statistically significant ($p = 0.057$ and $p = 0.119$).
- **BERTScore:** In contrast, the BERTScore difference ($p = 0.031$) indicates a weak but statistically significant tendency for the Polyline corridor to produce marginally more semantically aligned descriptions.

Overall, the two corridor definitions yield comparable model performance. As a result, either of the two corridor-based methods could be reasonably adopted as the geo-context representation in subsequent experiments. In this project, the POLY-COR (Polyline Corridor) configuration is selected for the following experiments, as it offers slightly higher semantic consistency and a more localized representation of the walking environment.

4.3.3 Experiment 3: Modality Input Analysis

Objective

The purpose of this experiment is to investigate how combining different input modalities influences the quality of generated POI descriptions. Specifically, this experiment evaluates the contribution of **spatial**, **visual**, and **perspective** information when added to the textual input (**Title**). It directly addresses the research questions posed in Section 1.4.

Setup

As this experiment focuses on analyzing the role of different **input modalities**, all configurations share the same encoder-fusion-decoder architecture introduced in Section 3.3. The experimental design inherits the optimal settings established in Experiments 1 and 2. Specifically, when a spatial modality is included, nearby POIs are retrieved using the Polyline Corridor method determined in Experiment 2. During inference, decoding parameters are fixed at `min_length = 10` and `max_length = 45`, following the configuration selected in Experiment 1 to ensure consistent generation length across all modalities.

TABLE 4.13: Configuration for Experiment 3.
All components follow the design in Section 3.3, with variation in the inputs.

Component	Configuration
Input modality	Detail in Table 4.14 with the spatial context being Polyline Corridor
Encoder	Following Section 3.3.1
Fusion module	Guide-Select fusion mechanism (Section 3.3.2).
Decoder (GPT-2)	Following Section 3.3.3 (with <code>min_length=10</code> , <code>max_length=45</code>)
Evaluation Metrics	BLEU, CIDEr, BERTScore.

This experiment employs the five modality configurations listed in Table 4.14. Finally, like Experiment 2, all configurations are evaluated using three primary metrics, **BLEU**, **CIDEr**, and **BERTScore**, which collectively measure lexical accuracy, content relevance, and semantic similarity to human-written POI descriptions.

TABLE 4.14: Input modality configurations evaluated in Experiment 3.

ID	Name	Description / Reference Section
T-G	Baseline: Title + Geo-context (Poly-line)	Reproduces the configuration of GSGM [1] using Title text and POLY-COR spatial input (Section 3.1.2).
T	Title only	Removes the geo-context modality to assess the dependence on spatial information.
T-I	Title + Image	Incorporates POI imagery encoded by a Vision Transformer to test the impact of visual cues.
T-G-I	Title + Geo-context + Image	Combines textual, spatial, and visual inputs through the cross-modal fusion layer.
T-G-I-P	Title + Geo-context + Image + Perspective	Extends the full multimodal setup with walker-perspective embeddings derived from route-level themes.

Results

Table 4.15 summarizes the mean scores of the three primary evaluation metrics across ten folds for each modality configuration. The results are presented in an aggregated form, emphasizing cross-modality trends rather than per-fold variations. Figure 4.4 complements this table by showing the distribution of scores across folds, revealing both central tendencies and variability for each metric.

TABLE 4.15: Average Metrics by Modality Configuration. Values represent mean scores across ten folds. Bold values indicate the best performance per metric.

Configuration	BLEU	CIDEr	BERTScore
T (Title only)	0.156	0.737	0.570
T-G (Title + Geo-context)	0.155	0.740	0.571
T-I (Title + Image)	0.153	0.763	0.576
T-G-I (Title + Geo-context + Image)	0.157	0.745	0.589
T-G-I-P (+ Perspective)	0.154	0.748	0.571

FIGURE 4.4: Boxplots of BLEU, CIDEr, BERTScore metrics across modality configurations.

The average results show that T-G-I achieves the highest BLEU and BERTScore, whereas T-I attains the strongest CIDEr. The boxplots reveal that BLEU differences among configurations are relatively small, with T-G-I maintaining the highest median, while T-I displays more variability. For CIDEr, T-I consistently outperforms other configurations, showing both the highest median and stable distribution. BERTScore distributions clearly separate T-G-I above the rest, confirming its semantic advantage.

In addition to reporting average scores, I conduct statistical significance testing to determine whether the observed differences between modality configurations are meaningful. Rather than performing exhaustive pairwise comparisons across all models, I focus on comparisons against the **baseline configuration (T-G)**, which reproduces the setup of GSGM [1]. This approach highlights whether incorporating additional modalities (image and perspective) yields significant improvements over the established baseline. The results of the Wilcoxon signed-rank tests are summarized in Table 4.16.

TABLE 4.16: Statistical test results comparing the baseline model (T-G) with other modality configurations across BLEU, CIDEr, and BERTScore.
(✓= significant difference, ✗= not significant)

Metric	Comparison	Statistic	p-value	Signif.
BLEU	T-G vs T	1.0	0.003906	✓
	T-G vs T-I	10.0	0.083984	✗
	T-G vs T-G-I	0.0	0.001953	✓
	T-G vs T-G-I-P	27.0	1.000000	✗
CIDEr	T-G vs T	21.0	0.556641	✗
	T-G vs T-I	2.0	0.005859	✓
	T-G vs T-G-I	21.0	0.556641	✗
	T-G vs T-G-I-P	18.0	0.375000	✗
BERTScore	T-G vs T	10.0	0.083984	✗
	T-G vs T-I	1.0	0.003906	✓
	T-G vs T-G-I	0.0	0.001953	✓
	T-G vs T-G-I-P	27.0	1.000000	✗

The Wilcoxon tests indicate that adding Geo-context to Title-only yields a significant improvement in BLEU, though not in CIDEr or BERTScore. Comparing T-G with T-I and T-G-I shows that image input provides significant gains in CIDEr and BERTScore, while the full multimodal combination (T-G-I) also improves BLEU and BERTScore significantly. In contrast, the perspective-augmented variant (T-G-I-P) does not show significant differences from the baseline. These results indicate that while visual and spatial inputs yield measurable improvements, the effect of perspective signals is less evident in quantitative metrics.

Nevertheless, the T-G-I-P combination can be treated as a special case, where the “best” result is not necessarily the objective best across all metrics, but rather reflects a specific narrative perspective that may intentionally prioritize certain experiential. To illustrate this, several examples of generated texts conditioned on different perspective inputs are presented in Section 5.3.

Chapter 5

Discussion

This chapter discusses the empirical findings presented in Chapter 4 in relation to the research aims and hypotheses introduced in Section 1.4. The discussion moves beyond numerical comparisons to provide conceptual insights into how different modalities (textual, visual, and spatial) jointly contribute to the generation of POI descriptions. Specifically, three key aspects are examined: the influence of visual modality on descriptive richness, the effect of alternative geo-context representations on the model’s performance, and the role of perspective signals in reflecting walkers’ subjective experiences.

5.1 Influence of Visual Modality on Descriptive Richness

The integration of visual information provides clear benefits to the model’s ability to generate more descriptive and content-rich POI texts. This finding directly addresses **Hypothesis 1**, which proposed that incorporating POI imagery would enhance the model’s understanding of the physical and atmospheric characteristics of places. The quantitative results from Experiment 3 support this hypothesis: configurations that include image input (**Title-Image** and **Title-Geo-Image**) outperform text-only or text-geo baselines across the three evaluation metrics. In particular, the **Title-Image** setup achieved the highest CIDEr score of **0.763** (vs. 0.740 for **Title-Geo** and 0.737 for **Title**), while the **Title-Geo-Image** model obtained the strongest semantic alignment, with a BERTScore of **0.589** and BLEU of **0.157**. However, the trends across the

three metrics are not fully consistent: the **Title-Image** configurations that perform best on CIDEr yield comparatively lower BLEU scores. This divergence highlights that each metric captures different dimensions of text quality, lexical overlap versus content relevance, and therefore we need a more detailed examination to interpret the results comprehensively.

With respect to individual metrics, the **Title-Image** configuration achieves the highest CIDEr score among all settings. CIDEr evaluates the similarity between a generated text and its human-written references by computing the weighted cosine similarity of TF-IDF n -gram vectors, thereby rewarding the presence of informative and distinctive content words rather than mere lexical overlap [79]. As such, a higher CIDEr value indicates that the generated description captures salient and content-rich details that humans also emphasize.

While these quantitative differences are informative, it is also important to understand why CIDEr is particularly meaningful in the context of this study. The relevance of CIDEr can be better understood by considering its original purpose and how POI descriptions are created in leisure walking contexts. CIDEr is initially designed for evaluating image captioning, rewarding descriptions that capture the key visual elements present in an image [79]. Interestingly, the process of writing POI descriptions shares a similar nature. Walkers often take photos during their journey and later compose the textual descriptions after completing the walk, using those photos to recall the places and experiences they encountered. As a result, the written descriptions frequently depict the same scenes shown in the images, combining factual visual details with personal impressions. This parallel makes CIDEr particularly meaningful for evaluating multi-modal models in this setting: when the image modality is integrated, a higher CIDEr score indicates that the generated descriptions align more closely with the visual content associated with each POI and are grounded in the same perceptual cues that guided human authors.

Another observation from the results is that the inclusion of geo-context does not further increase the CIDEr score when combined with images. This outcome can be partly explained by the characteristics of the CIDEr metric, which places stronger emphasis on visually grounded content. Because CIDEr rewards the use of distinctive n -grams corresponding to observable objects or scenery [79], the **Title-Image** configuration,

driven purely by visual cues, tends to produce descriptions that more directly reflect what is depicted in the POI image. When geo-context information is added, the model introduces details beyond the image frame, such as nearby facilities, landmarks, or environmental features, that enrich the description but shift its focus away from the strictly visual content that CIDEr primarily rewards. Consequently, the **Title-Geo-Image** configuration attains a slightly lower CIDEr score. However, this combination offers an opportunity for the model to integrate both visual and spatial cues, leading to a broader and more balanced understanding of each place, a pattern that becomes more evident when examined through the BERTScore results in the following.

Turning to the **BERTScore**, unlike BLEU or CIDEr, which evaluate lexical or n -gram similarity, BERTScore measures the contextual correspondence of meaning by comparing token embeddings in a high-dimensional semantic space. Therefore, a higher BERTScore reflects that the model captures not only the literal words used by human authors but also their underlying intent and descriptive focus [83].

When comparing the **Title-Image** and **Title-Geo** configurations, the BERTScore results indicate that the visual modality provides stronger semantic grounding than the spatial modality. Specifically, **Title-Image** achieves a higher BERTScore (with the statistical test result of $p = 0.0039 < 0.05$), showing that visual cues enable the model to generate descriptions more semantically aligned with human references. This can be attributed to the nature of images, which convey rich perceptual information, such as color, structure, texture, and atmosphere, that directly shapes how people perceive and describe places. In contrast, geo-context encoded as nearby POIs mainly supplies relational or categorical information (e.g., “close to a café” or “near a playground”), which contributes to factual completeness but offers less influence on the expressive and conceptual aspects of description. Therefore, the improvement of BERTScore in the visual configuration highlights that imagery plays a more substantial role than spatial context in enhancing semantic coherence and descriptive depth when generating POI texts.

Furthermore, the combination of visual and spatial modalities in the **Title-Geo-Image** configuration yields the highest BERTScore in all setups, with statistically significant improvement over the baseline setup. This improvement suggests that the integration enables the model to generate semantically richer and more coherent descriptions. Spatial context provides complementary information that situates visual observations within

their broader geographic environment. For example, connecting a “bench” in the image to its placement “by the river” or within a “public park.” In other words, the visual modality contributes the descriptive richness, and the spatial modality provides structure and situational relevance. This fusion of modalities helps the model produce text that aligns more closely with how humans conceptually perceive and describe places, combining what is seen with where it is situated.

It is notable that the **Title-Geo-Image** configuration also achieves the highest BLEU score, with a marginal absolute gain of only 0.001 compared to the baseline. Despite the small magnitude, this difference is statistically significant, confirming that the joint use of visual and spatial information enhances not only semantic alignment but also lexical precision. In contrast, neither **Title-Image** nor **Title-Geo** individually surpasses the text-only model in BLEU. The relatively high BLEU score of the **Title**-only model can be attributed to its reliance on familiar lexical patterns frequently observed in the training data. Without additional modalities, the model tends to reproduce common phrasing structures, resulting in higher n -gram overlap with reference texts. When either geo-context or image information is added individually, the model incorporates new spatial or visual content that diversifies the wording, often through paraphrases or alternative expressions tailored to describe appearance or location. As a result, lexical overlap with human-written descriptions decreases, leading to a reduction in BLEU despite potentially richer meaning. However, similar to the pattern observed with BERTScore, when all three modalities are combined, each plays a complementary role in shaping the final output. The **Title** provides a strong linguistic anchor that guides the overall theme and phrasing of the description, spatial cues establish a geographical context that guides the flow of the description, and visual features enrich word choice with vivid details. This balanced integration allows the model to produce sentences that remain lexically closer to human-written descriptions.

In summary, the inclusion of visual modality demonstrates a consistent positive effect across all three evaluation metrics, though with varying degrees of impact. The **Title-Image** configuration achieves the highest CIDEr score, indicating that image features help the model capture salient visual content aligned with human perception. The **Title-Geo-Image** setup attains the highest BERTScore and BLEU, suggesting that combining imagery with spatial cues further enhances both semantic coherence and lexical precision. In other words, these results confirm that visual information substantially

contributes to the descriptive richness of generated POI texts by providing perceptual grounding that complements textual and spatial inputs. This finding directly answers **Research Question 1** and supports **Hypothesis 1**, affirming that incorporating POI imagery enhances the model’s understanding of the physical and atmospheric characteristics of places.

5.2 Effect of Alternative Geo-context Representations

When discussing the role of image modality in the previous section, the contribution of spatial information is also presented. Specifically, the spatial modality is shown to enhance the overall contextual understanding, allowing the model to represent relationships and spatial nuances that pure visual grounding could not capture. This is evidenced by the **Title-Geo-Image** configuration achieving the highest BLEU and BERTScore values, as discussed in Section 5.1. Notably, the geo-context used in Experiment 3, the **Polyline Corridor** representation, is not identical to the spatial data employed in previous studies such as GSGM [1] or MMDG [8], which both adopted a fixed-radius approach. The choice of the Polyline Corridor representation is motivated by the findings of Experiment 2. In this section, I take a closer look at the results of this experiment to examine how alternative geo-context representations influence model performance.

First, the result shows that the density-aware radius approach outperforms the fixed-radius method. This is because the density-aware approach better aligns the spatial retrieval scale with the characteristics of different environments. Using a single fixed radius of 1000 m leads to strong spatial imbalance: in dense urban areas, it retrieves an excessive number of surrounding features, introducing irrelevant noise, whereas in rural regions, it often yields too few contextual elements to represent the local environment adequately. By contrast, the density-aware strategy dynamically adjusts the retrieval radius according to population density, smaller radii (100-200 m) for urban areas and larger ones (500-1000 m) for rural zones. This adaptive design reduces noise in dense urban areas and enhances representativeness in rural regions by balancing the number of nearby POIs retrieved across different spatial settings. In other words, by using smaller radii in built-up environments, it prevents the inclusion of excessive and irrelevant features, while larger radii in sparsely populated areas ensure sufficient contextual

coverage. As a result, the retrieved geo-context becomes cleaner, more balanced, and more contextually relevant, allowing the model to generate POI descriptions that are semantically richer and better aligned with reference texts, as reflected in the improved CIDEr and BERTScore metrics.

Although adjusting the retrieval radius according to population density yields moderate improvements compared to a fixed radius, it is not a reliable descriptor of walking environments. This is because population density captures residential concentration rather than the physical or experiential qualities of the environment. Two areas with similar density levels may differ substantially in their walkability, greenery, and availability of pedestrian amenities. Therefore, while density-aware adjustment helps to mitigate data imbalance, it remains an indirect and imperfect proxy for walking environments.

In contrast, route-based approaches provide a more intrinsic and meaningful representation of walking context. They capture spatial relationships along the walking path and reflect the linear progression of leisure routes, where nearby POIs are encountered sequentially rather than uniformly in all directions. Consequently, route-based contexts form a more coherent and perceptually grounded set of neighbouring POIs, enabling the model to generate descriptions that are semantically richer and more closely aligned with human-written references.

Among the two route-based approaches, the segment corridor method defines the local context as the straight line connecting the preceding and succeeding POIs, while the polyline corridor extends this representation to follow the route geometry. Although both capture the sequential nature of walking experiences, their geometric properties differ. The segment-based corridor emphasizes local continuity and is less affected by irregular route shapes, offering a concise and stable spatial window around each POI. In contrast, the polyline-based corridor provides a representation that follows the curvature of the route, potentially offering a more faithful depiction of complex paths but also introducing geometric redundancy where routes contain loops or sharp turns. Empirically, both methods yield comparable model performance, suggesting that the representation of walking context is robust to minor geometric variations.

Overall, the findings of Experiment 2 indicate that Route-based geo-context representations yield more contextually relevant and coherent descriptions than Radius-based alternatives. This highlights the importance of representing spatial context in a way

that mirrors how walkers perceive and interact with their environment. Beyond the quantitative findings, these results emphasise that geo-context is not a fixed construct but an adaptive representation that should reflect the spatial logic of the activity being modelled. In domains such as GSGM [1], which focus on static POIs like restaurants or hotels, spatial relevance is proximity-based. In contrast, leisure walking involves sequential and experiential interaction with space, where relevance arises from directional continuity and environmental immersion. Therefore, the optimal form of geo-context depends on how humans engage with space, whether through static observation or dynamic movement. Recognising this context dependency is crucial for designing multimodal generative models capable of adapting to different types of spatial narratives.

5.3 The Role of Perspective Signals in Reflecting Walkers’ Subjective Experiences

While spatial and visual modalities help the model capture what is seen and where it is located, they do not fully explain how a place is experienced. In leisure walking contexts, the subjective dimension, how walkers perceive and emotionally respond to places, forms an essential part of descriptive language. To further understand this aspect, this section provides a closer examination of the results obtained when perspective signals are added to the multimodal configuration (T-G-I-P). Rather than representing a new modality, perspective functions as a conditional textual input that conveys the thematic focus of a walk, such as “nature trail,” “historical interest,” or “park/garden”. The following analysis revisits the outcomes of adding this input and discusses how it influences the model’s generative behaviour beyond quantitative metrics.

As shown in Section 4.3.3, adding perspective signals does not lead to statistically significant improvements across BLEU, CIDEr, or BERTScore compared with the baseline configuration, and even results in slightly lower scores than the T-G-I model. A straightforward explanation is that perspective information may introduce additional noise into the model, thereby reducing metric performance. However, it is important to note that while perspective data may add a certain degree of semantic variability, such variability is unlikely to constitute random noise. This is because the perspective embeddings are categorical representations derived from a predefined set of thematic route features

rather than unstructured or free-form text inputs. Each perspective value encodes a consistent and interpretable concept, ensuring that this conditional input remains semantically coherent. Therefore, the lack of quantitative improvement cannot be simply attributed to random noise introduced by the perspective data;

Instead, a more plausible explanation lies in feature redundancy and data sparsity introduced by the additional conditional input. The inclusion of perspective embeddings increases the dimensionality of the multimodal representation without a corresponding expansion of training data. Consequently, the model must learn a higher-dimensional feature space with the same amount of supervision, which may lead to inefficient feature utilization. Moreover, because perspective tags are derived from route-level themes, the data distribution becomes clustered around a few dominant categories (Waterfront & Water bodies, Park/Garden or Historical Interest see Appendix C). This clustering reduces variability within each subset and weakens the model’s ability to generalize across perspectives. As a result, although perspective conditioning introduces semantic diversity at the dataset level, it does not provide sufficiently consistent or fine-grained cues at the POI level, thereby limiting its contribution to quantitative performance.

Importantly, the addition of perspective information is intended to explore semantic nuance rather than to pursue further metric improvements. Therefore, its influence is better understood by examining the linguistic variation it introduces in generated outputs. Specifically, the objective here is to determine whether conditioning the model with different perspectives leads to noticeable variations in generated POI descriptions, and whether those variations align with the intended thematic viewpoint.

The fifteen examples, each corresponding to one of the perspective categories and presented in Appendix D, demonstrate that the model is capable of expressing nuanced thematic variation across different perspective conditions. In several cases, the generated descriptions effectively adapt their lexical choices and narrative focus to match the intended viewpoint.

For instance, under the *Waterfront & Water bodies* perspective, the model successfully emphasizes environmental features associated with water scenery:

POI: Wetlands viewing platform

Generated text: For a good view across the wetlands, take advantage of the viewing platform near the end of the Stock Bridge.

Similarly, under the *Historical interest* perspective, the generated text naturally incorporates temporal markers and restoration context, reflecting an awareness of historical framing:

POI: Community Garden - 56 Hardey Rd

Generated text: Built in 1880 as a private residence, the garden was first organised by the Hardey family in 1876 and is still used as a community space today.

These examples illustrate that when perspective-related cues are salient and well represented in the training data, the model can adjust its linguistic framing to express the corresponding thematic viewpoint with considerable nuance.

However, this semantic nuance is not consistent across all perspectives. In some cases, particularly those with limited data coverage or ambiguous lexical signals, the conditioning perspective fails to produce the intended thematic framing. For example, the following description was generated under the *Drinking water available* perspective:

POI: Picnic area and oval

Generated text: This is a lovely place to have a picnic with your family and friends.

The generated text aligns more closely with the theme of a *Picnic spot* rather than the intended perspective. This deviation likely results from the scarcity of training samples for the *Drinking water available* perspective (only about 140 POIs in the dataset) and from the lexical bias introduced by the POI title ("Picnic area and oval").

Another illustrative case involves generating multiple descriptions for the same POI under different perspective conditions. This setup allows observation of how perspective signals guide the model's linguistic framing while other inputs remain constant. The POI used for this experiment is **Austin Park** with five selected perspectives, and the generated outputs are summarised in Table 5.1.

TABLE 5.1: Generated descriptions for the same POI (*Austin Park*) under different perspective inputs

Perspective	Generated Description
Park / Garden	A park with a playground, tennis courts, amphitheatre, water fountain, BBQ, and seating. This canopy provides shade on a hot day and is a great place to picnic.
Historical interest	Established in 1958, the facility was used for various sporting events. It is now the home of the Sneydes Park Tennis Club.
Dog leash-off area	This gets dogs to be on leash until you enter the fenced-off dog park, which is massive and includes a small playground for dogs.
Drinking water available	A park with a playground, tennis courts, amphitheatre, water fountain, BBQ, and seating. This canopy provides shade on a hot day and is a great place to picnic.
Playground	A park with a playground, tennis courts, amphitheatre, water fountain, BBQ, and seating. This canopy provides shade on a hot day and is a great place to picnic.

The result shows that using the same input information but conditioning on five different perspectives, the model generated three distinct descriptions. Particularly, *Historical interest* and *Dog friendly* produce highly specific and distinctive descriptions, while *Park / Garden*, *Drinking water available* and *Playground* result in the identical output. Interestingly, the content of these identical descriptions still remains relevant to their assigned perspectives, as the shared text includes elements such as “park,” “playground,” and “water fountain,” which are semantically appropriate for *Park / Garden*, *Playground*, and *Drinking water available*. It means that model can exhibit semantic nuance based on the provided perspective; however, the variation is not evenly distributed across all perspectives.

The uneven variation across perspectives can be attributed to differences in their semantic distinctiveness. Perspectives such as *Historical interest* or *Dog friendly* exhibit clear and domain-specific lexical cues (temporal expressions, heritage references, or pet-related

terms) that are distinguishable within the dataset. In contrast, several perspectives are semantically overlapping, describing similar recreational environments and amenities. For instance, *Park / Garden*, *Playground*, and *Drinking water available* often co-occur with descriptions that mention picnic areas, water fountains, or shaded seating, which are linguistically and conceptually similar. As a result, the conditioning signals of these perspectives are not sufficiently discriminative, leading the model to generate identical outputs across them. This suggests that the unevenness observed here partly stems from the design of the perspective features themselves, some being too semantically similar to provide distinct conditioning effects.

Overall, these findings indicate that perspective conditioning helps the model adjust its wording and thematic focus according to the given viewpoint, but the effect is uneven across perspectives. Perspectives with clear and distinctive meanings, such as *Historical interest* and *Dog friendly*, lead to specific and well-aligned descriptions, whereas those that overlap semantically, like *Park / Garden*, *Playground*, and *Drinking water available*, tend to produce similar outputs. This suggests that the model can respond to high-level semantic cues, but struggles to separate perspectives that describe comparable environments.

In addition, the size and balance of the dataset also contribute to this unevenness: when certain perspectives dominate the training data, the model becomes more familiar with their linguistic patterns, resulting in more coherent descriptions for those categories. Conversely, perspectives with very limited data do not provide enough evidence for the model to learn distinctive linguistic associations, leading to less relevant outputs.

These two factors highlight the importance of designing both a balanced dataset and a semantically distinctive set of perspective categories. Ensuring that each perspective is sufficiently represented and meaningfully differentiated from others would allow the model to generate more consistent and perspective-aware descriptions.

Taken together, these results address **Research Question 2** by showing that perspective information can influence the generation process but its impact depends on both the semantic clarity and data balance of the perspective categories. Consequently, **Hypothesis 2** is only partially supported: perspective conditioning enhances thematic diversity and viewpoint awareness in the generated text, but its effect remains limited when the conditioning signals are semantically overlapping or unevenly distributed in the training

data. Moreover, the results for evaluation metrics (BLEU, CIDEr, and BERTScore) show no statistically significant improvements, indicating that perspective information does not consistently lead to outputs that are more closely aligned with the reference descriptions.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

This thesis investigated the automatic generation of descriptions for POIs in leisure walking contexts through multimodal learning.

The study begins with the construction of a comprehensive POI dataset that integrates user-generated descriptions, geographic context derived from OpenStreetMap (OSM), and images collected from the WalkingMaps platform. Each photo is originally contributed by walkers themselves, ensuring that the data authentically reflects real-world walking experiences and perspectives.

Building on this dataset, the research proposed and evaluated a multimodal generation framework that integrates textual, spatial, and visual information to produce human-like POI descriptions. To the best of my knowledge, this is the first study to incorporate POI imagery into a multimodal text generation model for POI description and the first to apply such a model specifically within the context of leisure walking. Through a series of experiments, the study systematically examined how different modalities and spatial representations influence descriptive quality and contextual coherence, and how perspective conditioning shapes the expressive characteristics of generated texts.

The empirical findings confirm that incorporating visual features enhances descriptive richness, spatial context contributes structural coherence, and perspective signals introduce experiential nuance. In addition, the results of experiments also suggest that adding geo-context does not distort the semantic meaning of the generated text. Instead, it enhances the overall contextual understanding, allowing the model to represent relationships and spatial nuances that pure visual grounding cannot capture. Importantly,

the effectiveness of geo-context depends on how it is represented relative to the target activity. In the case of leisure walking, spatial context must capture the sequential and experiential nature of movement rather than static proximity, as walkers perceive places along a route rather than within a fixed radius. This highlights that geo-context representation should be adapted to the spatial logic of the activity being modeled, ensuring that the retrieved contextual information reflects how humans actually experience the environment.

Another key finding is that the integration of visual and spatial modalities leads to more human-like and context-aware POI descriptions. The complementary roles of these two modalities, visual features enriching perceptual detail and spatial context providing structural coherence, allow the model to generate text that more closely mirrors how people perceive and describe places in real-world settings.

These results directly address **Research Question 1** and support **Hypothesis 1**, which proposed that incorporating visual information would enhance the model’s ability to produce richer, more perceptually grounded, and semantically coherent POI descriptions. Overall, the findings highlight that multimodal and context-aware modeling provides a promising direction for generating POI descriptions that are not only accurate and coherent but also reflective of how walkers experience their surroundings.

In contrast, **Hypothesis 2** is only partially supported. The qualitative analysis of generated samples shows that the model can express semantic nuances according to the provided perspectives, but this behaviour is not consistent across all categories. Its effectiveness largely depends on the distinctiveness of the perspective signals and the balance of their representation in the dataset. Perspectives with clear and unique semantic cues lead to distinct and well-aligned descriptions, whereas semantically overlapping or underrepresented perspectives tend to produce similar outputs.

Consequently, **Research Question 2** is addressed with a conditional conclusion: the model is capable of integrating walkers’ perspectives into the generation process, but the reliability of this effect are influenced by how clearly the perspectives are defined and how evenly they are distributed in the data. This finding underlines the need for refining the design of perspective features and improving data balance to achieve more consistent and perspective-aware generation.

Future work could focus on two main directions.

The first is improving the definition and assignment of perspective features. In this study, perspectives were assigned using a combination of three automatic tagging strategies, but the assigned labels were not systematically evaluated after assignment. As a result, the accuracy and consistency of the perspective annotations could not be fully verified.

In the future, we can enhance the perspective assignment process by:

- **Post-assignment evaluation:** A evaluation stage could be introduced to identify and correct mismatched or low-confidence labels could be incorporated. This would involve reassessing and reassigning perspectives for ambiguous samples to reduce label noise and improve supervision quality.
- **Manual annotation:** Manual labeling by domain experts could be used to build a smaller but higher-quality benchmark subset for validation and model fine-tuning.
- **Multi-perspective representation:** Relaxing the current one-to-one assumption that links each description to a single perspective could be a potential improvement. In practice, a single POI description may express multiple perspectives simultaneously. For example, a riverside park can convey themes of *nature trail*, *family-friendly*, and *waterfront*. Supporting multi-label or soft-assignment representations would better capture this natural overlap and provide the model with richer contextual supervision.

The second task for future work could be improving and expanding the dataset. The current dataset primarily relies on WalkingMaps platform¹ collected within the state of Victoria, Australia, with only limited coverage beyond this region. Consequently, the raw corpus, containing around 19,000 POIs, reflects a relatively narrow geographic and cultural scope.

To build a more diverse and representative dataset, future research could integrate data from other platforms such as *Slow Ways*² (United Kingdom) and *Rankers*³ (New Zealand), which provide user-generated route information and descriptive content across different landscapes and cultural contexts. Leveraging these complementary sources

¹<https://walkingmaps.com.au/>

²<https://beta.slowways.org/>

³<https://www.rankers.co.nz/>

would yield a much larger and more heterogeneous POI dataset, encompassing various styles of walking experiences and environmental settings. Such expansion would not only increase linguistic and geographic diversity but also enable the model to generalize more effectively across different walking scenarios worldwide.

Appendix A

Full Keyword Inventory for Thematic Feature Scoring

This appendix provides the complete set of keywords used in the **Rule-based Scoring** method described in Section 3.2.2. These keywords are manually curated to represent the 15 thematic features relevant to leisure walking contexts (e.g., *Park/Garden*, *Playground*, *Historical interest*).

The purpose of this appendix is to make explicit the full keyword inventory that underpins the rule-based component of the thematic feature extraction pipeline. The entire keyword set is listed below.

Feature	Keywords
Public Transport	public transport, bus, tram, train, railway, station, metro, stop, transit
Drinking water available	drinking water, water tap, fountain, bubbler, hydration, refill, water station
Public toilets	toilet, toilets, restroom, bathroom, wc, lavatory, amenities, public convenience, loo, washroom

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Feature	Keywords (continued)
Nature trail	nature trail, walking track, hiking trail, bushwalk, path, trail, footpath, walkway, bush trail, track
Park / Garden	park, garden, botanical, reserve, green space, arboretum, play field, open space, trees, tree, shade
Playground	playground, slide, swing, climbing, monkey bars, play equipment, kids play, children play, play area
Seating available	bench, benches, seat, seating, rest area, sitting place, chair, shelter, picnic table
Pram friendly	pram, stroller, pushchair, baby buggy, pram friendly, accessible path, buggy
Historical interest	historical, heritage, memorial, monument, plaque, historic site, war memorial, history, landmark, centenary, anniversary, named after, built in, established, opened in
Local treasures	local treasure, hidden gem, unique, special site, local icon, famous spot, landmark, school, primary school, library, post office, shopping centre, milk bar
Picnic spot	picnic, bbq, barbecue, tables, picnic area, family lunch, grassed area, picnic table, shelter, lawn
Dog off-leash area	dog, dogs, puppy, pet, off-leash, off leash, dog park, dog walking
Art and culture	art, sculpture, statue, mural, gallery, culture, exhibition, public art, installation, street art
Waterfront & Water bodies	lake, river, creek, stream, pond, lagoon, waterway, wetland, coast, seaside, beach, shore, bay, harbour, harbor, foreshore, promenade, boardwalk, pier, jetty, marina, baths, sea baths, ocean, sea, estuary, inlet, lookout, viewpoint, cliff, view

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Feature	Keywords (continued)
Accessible walk	accessible, wheelchair, disability access, mobility, easy access, flat path, accessible walk, ramp, traffic lights, crossing, pedestrian crossing, tripping hazard

In total, the inventory consists of 171 keywords across 15 features. This set is used in both the **Rule-based Scoring** (direct keyword matching) and the **Semantic Similarity** method (embedding-based matching with SentenceTransformer). By making the full list available here, the study ensures transparency and allows future replication or refinement of the feature extraction pipeline.

Appendix B

Examples of Feature Scoring Outputs

This appendix provides illustrative outputs of the three thematic feature extraction methods (rule-based matching, semantic similarity, and zero-shot classification), as well as the ensemble combination for one representative POI. The example POI is “*The new path*” (poi_id: 3852_14944) on the Bondi to Coogee Coastal Walk, NSW. Its description is:

“Finally, in 2021 a new path was created for the 6,000 or so people who walk this path each day (there was no path there before).”

Rule-based Scores

Feature	Rule-based Count
Historical interest	1
Nature trail	3

TABLE B.1: Rule-based keyword matches for POI “The new path”.

Semantic Similarity Scores

Feature	Similarity Score
Public Transport	0.394
Drinking water available	0.158
Public toilets	0.182
Nature trail	0.551
Park / Garden	0.254
Playground	0.334
Seating available	0.160
Pram friendly	0.362
Historical interest	0.247
Local treasures	0.247
Picnic spot	0.248
Dog off-leash area	0.380
Art and culture	0.370
Waterfront & Water bodies	0.408
Accessible walk	0.476

TABLE B.2: Full semantic similarity scores for POI “The new path”.

Zero-shot Classification Scores

Feature	Zero-shot Score
Accessible walk	0.233
Historical interest	0.153
Public Transport	0.113
Pram friendly	0.111
Art and culture	0.056
Waterfront & Water bodies	0.056
Park / Garden	0.055
Local treasures	0.054
Nature trail	0.039
Seating available	0.030
Drinking water available	0.027
Playground	0.023
Public toilets	0.018
Picnic spot	0.017
Dog off-leash area	0.016

TABLE B.3: Zero-shot classification scores for POI “The new path”.

Ensemble Result

For the ensemble method, scores from the three approaches are combined. An illustrative combination rule is:

$$\text{ensemble_score}(f) = w_r \cdot \text{rule}(f) + w_s \cdot \text{similarity}(f) + w_z \cdot \text{zeroshot}(f),$$

where w_r, w_s, w_z are method-specific weights. Table B.4 shows the resulting ensemble scores using equal weights for demonstration.

Feature	Ensemble Score
Nature trail	1.30
Historical interest	0.47
Accessible walk	0.24
Waterfront & Water bodies	0.29
Dog off-leash area	0.27
...	...

TABLE B.4: Illustrative ensemble scores for POI “The new path”. Only top features are shown; full scores are computed for all features.

Appendix C

Distribution of Route-Level Perspectives

Table [C.1](#) summarize the frequency of route-level themes extracted from the WalkingMaps dataset.

TABLE C.1: Distribution of route-level perspective features

Perspective Feature	Number of Routes
Waterfront & Water bodies	2865
Park / Garden	2163
Nature trail	2129
Historical interest	2123
Accessible walk	1011
Art and culture	929
Pram friendly	707
Local treasures	665
Public Transport	655
Picnic spot	552
Seating available	472
Playground	408
Public toilets	239
Dog off-leash area	234
Drinking water available	136

As shown, the data are heavily skewed toward a few dominant themes such as *Waterfront & Water bodies*, *Park / Garden*, and *Nature trail*, each appearing in over 2,000 routes. In contrast, several features like *Drinking water available* or *Dog off-leash area* occur in fewer than 300 instances. This imbalance causes the learned representation of perspectives to cluster around these dominant categories, leading to data sparsity for minor ones.

Appendix D

Examples of Generated Texts under Perspective Conditioning

This appendix presents fifteen representative examples of POI descriptions generated under different perspective conditions. Each example corresponds to one of the perspective categories used in the dataset.

TABLE D.1: Generated POI descriptions with perspective inputs

Perspective	POI Title	Generated Text	Commentary	Assessment
Nature trail	The new path	<i>It's a new path that has been recently laid, making it a bit easier to walk and to protect the bush.</i>	Describes a newly built natural trail, mentioning easier walking and bush protection.	Aligned
Park / Garden	Conservation	<i>As the bush regenerates animal numbers grow. Here a Black Wallaby takes pause on the track.</i>	Highlights ecological regeneration and wildlife, typical of park or garden contexts.	Aligned
Accessible walk	Accessible car parking entrance	<i>There are 5 dedicated accessible car parks in the main car park. They have direct, ramped access into the all abilities playscape.</i>	Focuses on accessibility features such as ramps and designated parking.	Aligned
Waterfront & Water bodies	Wetlands viewing platform	<i>For a good view across the wetlands, take advantage of the viewing platform near the end of the Stock Bridge.</i>	Depicts a viewpoint overlooking wetlands, emphasizing water-related scenery.	Aligned
Seating available	Palais Theatre	<i>An outstanding example of the work of Bohringer, Taylor and Johnson, one of the most important and prolific cinema architectural firms in Australia.</i>	Focuses on architectural significance, without reference to seating or resting spots.	Not Aligned
Picnic spot	View across the river	<i>The landscape to the north sees the foothills of the Strathbogie Tablelands. The south sees the foothills of the Great.</i>	Describes scenic surroundings but omits picnic facilities or activities.	Partially Aligned
Historical interest	Community Garden - 56 Hardey Rd	<i>Built in 1880 as a private residence, the garden was first organised by the Hardey family in 1876 and is still used as a.</i>	Incorporates clear historical context and dates, highlighting heritage.	Aligned
Public Transport	Granite Roadway	<i>This roadway is very impressive and makes the walk easier place to start. It is well maintained and well maintained.</i>	Describes a roadway with maintenance details but no public transport cues.	Not Aligned
Local treasures	Mai Lan Bakery	<i>The bakery specialises in tasty meat and salad rolls, pastries and meals.</i>	Focuses on a popular local bakery and its specialties.	Aligned
Drinking water available	Picnic area and oval	<i>This is a lovely place to have a picnic with your family and friends.</i>	Refers to a picnic area without any mention of drinking water availability.	Not Aligned
Art and culture	Indigenous boy by Adnate	<i>The Indian boy by Adnate grew up to be leader of the Barrabool Tribe, a notable athlete and enthusiastic games participant.</i>	Combines artistic reference (Adnate) with cultural storytelling.	Aligned
Playground	Overlook of Playground Reserve	<i>Here you will get a good view of the playground and the natural surrounds.</i>	Explicitly mentions a playground and its view.	Aligned
Dog off-leash area	Kingsford Smith Ulm Reserve	<i>A lovely spot to rest and imagine life in Jean Gailbraith's day.</i>	Mentions relaxation and nostalgia but no reference to dogs or leash-free zones.	Not Aligned
Pram friendly	Carry binoculars	<i>The binoculars are useful in many ways. First off, you can see the sunset and when the sun is behind it, you can see.</i>	Describes sightseeing but omits accessibility or stroller-friendly cues.	Not Aligned
Public toilets	Corben Oval public toilets	<i>These public toilets are not signed as accessible. However, the internal cubicle is large with bilateral rails (door of 0.8 meters wide).</i>	Provides detailed information about toilet accessibility.	Aligned

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